

Changing Perception on Turkey in Middle East under the Light of Bilateral Political Agreements

CHANGING PERCEPTION BETWEEN TURKEY AND IRAN, SAUDI ARABIA AND EGYPT

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Bütün dünyanın dikkatleri bu bölgede yoğunlaşmıştır. Ülkeler ve ticari markalar kamuoyunda nasıl algılandıklarını, imajlarını çok önemsemektedirler. Ayrıca, küreselleşen dünyada imaj ve algılama; hem siyasi hem de ekonomik ve kültürel alanlarda oldukça etkili olabilmektedir

Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu'daki gelişmelere tepkisinin analizi de bu noktadan hareketle yapılmalıdır. Yeni Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu politikası, "Yeni Osmanlılık" olarak özetlenebilecek şekilde, uygulayıcıların "yeni coğrafya" algılarının bir parçası olarak kurgulanmıştır.

Bu şekilde oluşturulan politikalar şimdi derinden yaralıdır ve siyaset yapıcılarını; Ortadoğu ile ötesinin gerçeklikleri üzerine kurulmuş yeni/yenilenmiş dış politika oluşturmanın güçlüğü ile karşı karşıya bırakmıştır.

Yeni küresel düzen ihtiyaç duyduğu mekanizmaları yaratmaya çalışırken ulus devlet bu yeni oluşum içerisinde "yavaşça yok olacaktı". "Yeni coğrafya"nın bu tür yorumlarının etrafında Türk dış politikası, "komşularla sıfır sorunlu ilişkiler" gibi geniş, esnek ve muğlak kavramlarla formüle edilmiştir. Türkiye çok güçlü iç baskılara dayanabilen bir anayasal sisteme, canlı bir ekonomiye ve meşru bir hükümete sahiptir.

Türkiye laikliğe önem vermektedir ve aynı zamanda ulusal gurura da sahiptir. Ordusu sivilin kontrolindedir. Türkiye istisna olmak üzere Orta Doğu'daki tüm ülkeler meşruiyet sorunları yaşamaktadırlar

Anahtar sözcükler: Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu Politikaları, Mısır, İran ve Suudi Arabistan

ABSTRACT

Changing Perception on Turkey in Middle East under the Light of Bilateral Political Agreements CHANGING PERCEPTION BETWEEN TURKEY AND IRAN, SAUDI ARABIA AND EGYPT (2002 – 2014)

The attention of entire world concentrates on this region. Countries and trademarks care very much how they are perceived and their images in the public. Furthermore, the image and perception in the globalized world may be effective in both political and economical and cultural areas.

Analysis of Turkey's reaction toward the developments in Middle East should be made from this point of view. The Middle East policy of new Turkey is built as a part of "new geography" perception of the executors so that it may be summarized as "Neo-Ottoman".

The policies, which are determined in such way, is deeply wounded now, and the policy-makers encounter with difficulty of creating the new/renewed foreign policy which is established on the reality of Middle East and beyond.

As the new global order tries to create the mechanisms which it needs, the nation-state would "melt away slowly" within this new formation. Turkish foreign policy is formulated with the wide, flexible and ambiguous concepts such as "zero problematic relations with the neighbors" around such comments of "new geography". Turkey has the constitutional system, live economy and legal government which are durable against very powerful internal pressures.

Turkey gives importance to the secularism and also has a national proud. Its army is under the control of civilians. Except Turkey, all countries in Middle East experience the legitimacy problems

Keywords: Turkey's Middle East Policies, Egypt, Iran and Saudi Arabia

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(2002 – 2014)

*In this PhD Dissertation,
changing perception between Egypt, Saudi Arabia and Turkey
that are important actors of Middle East region
under the light of bilateral agreements which are concluded after 2002*

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INTRODUCTION

Image and perception take an important place in the societies and interstate relations. Countries and trademarks care very much how they are perceived and their images in the public. Furthermore, the image and perception in the globalized world may be effective in both political and economical and cultural areas. For example, as a democratic, safe and developed country image is arouse more respect in the international area, it means that the views of that country attract more attention in the world, and it contributes to that country's export through much more consumption of its products and brands, and to the economy through touristic visits. Even, upon its views are adopted, that country also gets to become the focus of interest. Since the cost of wars is very high and gradually decreases, it is tried to solve many issues in connection with public diplomacy and positive image, not with brute force in the international area.

In the globalization era, "geography" is still important, but recently, it has different meaning. Today, "new grography", which shapes the Turkey's foreign policy, has a meaning beyond geo-extension regarding the easily accessible fast travel meanings, common internet, media and social media, multi-channel TVs, fast movement of humans and capital; gradually increasing knowledge of business world about the world.

The foreign policy of Turkey, located in a strategic geograph where three continents meet, is also determined by this geography historically. In other words, "new geography" is partly related to economic and partly to political, social and cultural areas. Recently, the "security" concept is also added to them as a new parameter. However, we should emphasize that this security concept is different than the concept of military defense during the Cold War. This new type of "security" concept is associated with the individual freedoms and rights and is brought to forefront in determining the international relations. So, the new global structuring offers an environment that requires the analysis of international relations only via multi-layered social relations and evaluation of which is economic and not economic, and which is political and cultural and religious elements, all. ¹

¹¹Sedat Aybar, Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu Politikası ve Yeni Coğrafya algısı, http://tr.boell.org/sites/default/files/downloads/sedat_aybar_persp.2_tr.pdf Accession Date 15.06.2015

It is difficult to understand Middle East where Turkey is located, because understanding Middle East is not a pure scientific curiosity, but is a history to reestablish the political and social topography of region in a form which is consistent with the political interventions. Establishing an approach, which excludes the remnants from this history, requires a theoretical preliminary preparation. The steps, taken without this preparation, arise in an intellectual platform which is determined by the orientalism, even if it is formed with the naïve and apolitic motivations.

One may say that the people's hearts and mind should be won in order to support the followed policies of new parameters of "new geography". So indeed, implementing the successful policies in the new age is only possible by mobilizing the public, country's human and social capital. From this point of view, it is clear that any foreign policy analysis, policy-makers should start with understanding how they perceive this "new geography". In particular, it is important to analyze how they evaluate the economical, political, cultural structures which will help to mobilize the public support for a successful foreign policy.²

Until 2002, the course of Turkey's relations with West has always been the essential determinative element in Turkey's policy toward Middle East. Turkey, which deemed fit to not intervene to the Middle Eastern problems regarding its security until 1950s, considered that the active Western support was beneficial for its national interests, since it perceived a threatening from Soviet Union during 1950s. Turkey needed to diversify its foreign policy, when it had the problematic relations with West or didn't obtain the assistance/see the value which Turkey expected. Until 2002, Turkey's foreign policy toward Middle East has been formed by the first degree security concerns. After 2002 when Ak Party came to power alone, the changing international and regional equilibriums allowed Turkey to be interested in region.

As decreasing of the weigh of security concerns in Turkish foreign policy decreases the dependency of Turkey to West, it increases the efficiency of Turkey in near abroad, notably in Middle East. In this context, Turkey concluded many political, cultural and commercial agreements with the countries in region comparing with pre-2002.

Analysis of Turkey's reaction toward the developments in Middle East should be made from this point of view. The Middle East policy of new Turkey is built as a part of "new

²Aybar andOzgoker (2009): "Batı Enerji Güvenliği ve Türkiye", (Energy Security of the Western World), Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, Sayı: 2, Cilt 11, ss. 319–334.

geography” perception of the executors so that it may be summarized as “Neo-Ottoman”.³ The policies, which are determined in such way, is deeply wounded now, and the policy-makers encounter with difficulty of creating the new/renewed foreign policy which is established on the reality of Middle East and beyond.

The epistemological roots of Turkish foreign policy within the New Geography and Turkish foreign policy during Cold War were widely formulated and determined within the scope of Western Alliance based on the strategic framework of NATO. Disintegration of Soviet Unions and ending of Cold War after disintegration didn't create the formations which would settle various international disputes with the mechanisms and rules that their borders were determined within a certain legal, political order.

The international system, existing from that day to today, reflects a character which solves various problems on the ad hoc basis. It is clear that Turkey's traditional status quoist foreign policy should also have changed so as creating the power relations consistent with “new international environment” where there were water and energy resources available at the center in such complicated, negotiated world.⁴

Middle East is not a concept which we produce, even not a geographical definition. Even if the term Middle East was entered to the literature for the purpose of defining “Neareast” regions in 1902, it is a political description which is widely used after World War II. Despite the fact that Turkey turns its face toward West and tries to find a place in EU, it is a Middle East country in the world or at least, in the eyes of those who produce this concept. Turkey must live with this reality.

In fact, as being supposed, being Middle Eastern or being related to it is not a disadvantage. Those, who exclude Turkey from this concept, unfortunately, also don't have the history knowledge. If those experts looked at the history briefly, then they would see that the Western welfare states, which Turkey tried to reach to and to make like them today, developed by examining Middle East that was the geography of ancient empires throughout the history. Were Roma and Byzantium during mediavel, Portugal, Spain, France, UK, Italy, Germany during new contemporary ages, and was USA during modern times not interested in this region? Did they not intervene to the internal affairs of these regions, and did they not

³Sedat Aybar, Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu Politikası ve Yeni Coğrafya algısı, http://tr.boell.org/sites/default/files/downloads/sedat_aybar_persp.2_tr.pdf Accession Date 23.06.2015

⁴Sedat Aybar, Türkiye'nin Ortadoğu Politikası ve Yeni Coğrafya algısı, http://tr.boell.org/sites/default/files/downloads/sedat_aybar_persp.2_tr.pdf Accession Date 20.06.2015

protect those who felt sympathy to them in the region and not establish the alliance against others?

If the mentality is fed only by which are visible, and if it disregards other information and even the historical experience, then it is unavoidable to enter to the cul-de-sac. So, let's remind once more again, none of aforesaid countries that are shown as the examples for Turkey are interested in Middle East only on the basis of natural resources and natural wealthes. Of course, one may say that this is the imperialist interest, but Turkey doesn't have such intention, even it would be a dishonor as a defense reflex. One may agree upon this judgement, but it is not enough to explain the situations both in the past and today.

Besides Crusades in the past, the "Eastern Question", which we expect that Turkish intellectuals know, is a strategy that was suggested in order to be interested in Jarusalem and vicinity during 19th century and includes the plans to disintegrate Ottoman State internally. Ottoman State was subjected to double-direction attacks on Jarusalem. As European states (especially UK, France and Russia) tried to create the basis for intervention pretending the sacred spaces on one hand, Zionists prepared the plans in order to achieve their historical goals on the other hand.

Ottoman State stood those plans with its sensitivity and balance policies for a long time and Jarusalem could be protected. However, the bare truth, which everybody knows, is that even though it was not who started the war and its territory was not the primary fronts, all of the Eastern Question and Zionist goals were achieved at the end of World War I. Today, there is already a new geography, namely Middle East geography. So, how can we be apart ourselves from the entirety which we come out from?⁵

Jarusalem's Ottoman Governor issued a report to the government in Istanbul and summarized the situation there. His findings would be valid for ever and ever. Jarusalem's Ottoman Governor, Kemal Bey, says:

The attention of whole world is concentrated on this region. (Of course, if we look at it from today, we immediately remember the resources which Middle East possesses and we acknowledge this judgement. Whereas, he talks about very different matter). All attentions

⁵ Zekeriya Kurşun, Ortadoğu Neden Vazgeçilmezdir? <http://www.ordaf.org/ortadogu-neden-vazgecilmezdir> .
Accession Date 24. 07.2014

would be concentrated on Jarusalem and its surrounding geography (Middle East) today, tomorrow and in the future for ever and ever, because: (with his own words)

- This geography is Cevalangâh-i Musa. (It is the route where St. Moses gets about)
- This geography is Mehd-i İsa. (Where Jesus Christ was born)
- This geography is the scene of Mirac-i Muammedi. (It is the place where St. Mohammed ascended to heaven) You see, even if all of the grounds, which appear later and make Middle East important, are eliminated, then the interest in this region will never end due to the aforesaid reasons. Turkey has a historical responsibility on each light which is on and and disintegration of each family in Middle East and Africa. Even if we ignore or deny it, then the history will record this responsibility.

Turkey has both physical and love bonds with these two geographies. Almost all of the Middle Eastern people and most of Africans are Muslim. The historical bonds of Turkey with this geography were established on the memories which were powerful and positive that would support the new relations. These geographies are within the extension of Turkey's historical depth. When Turks came to the West from fatherlands, after they established their homes and first political organizations in Africa and then, Middle East (Iraq-Syria), they, finally, settled in Anatolia.

It should be remembered that the first place, where Turks established the state before Anatolia, was Egypt. Namely, Turks gain the power to stay in Anatolia there. They were able to an Anatolian-centered world state, Ottoman State with which they gained in Egypt. This geography is the natural alliance of Turkey. However, it had been neglected and even been forgotten due to various reasons for a long time.

The scientific researches on this field are insufficient in our country. As our universities try to overcome many problems or since they cannot change the mentality, they cannot establish the institutions that would do the researches on this field. May be, the limited number of Institute, and Research and Application Center, which are established with bona fide initiatives, are not sufficient to do research with unskillful employees. However, there are thousands of youngsters who wish to know and to do the researches on those subjects. Even if there are lectures related to Middle East and Africa through fully individual initiatives in the programs of some universities, since it is not allowed them to be institutionalized, they may not produce the expected results.

Unless the programs, which will follow each other at bachelor, master degrees and PhD, and the specialization areas related to Middle East and Africa at the associate professorship level, are not established, these individual endeavours will unavoidably be wasted. Our scientific level and specialization on this field fall very far behind the Turkish perception in Middle East and Africa.⁶

Turkish media generally moves after completion of development of the events. The problems of region are, time to time, discussed less or much in various columns or programs, but there is not any column/program which is completely devoted to Middle East and Africa. Even though there are some documentaries which are broadcasted in the visual media, they are the archive programs which are not updated.

The tragic side of issue is that the experts on these fields are either directly employed or state their opinions as the guest author/speaker in the world media. There are very less number of journalists who are specialized on this field in our country. Those, who carry out the scientific works related to the field, are not complimented or are considered as the “material” which only fills a column/screen. The necessary importance is not given to the work which they do, and even not esteemed.

Whereas, Turkey is located at the intersection point of energy resources and natural gas pipelines, flow from Central Asia and Iran toward Europe.⁷ Energy dimension of “New Geography” changes Turkey toward the economic cooperation, especially within the context of energy resources and pushes Turkey more powerfully to the gravitational field of USA that is the Turkey’s strategic alliance. This is consistent with USA’s new security architecture.

If one considers the problematic situation of US economy today, then it may be seen how Washington needs its alliances rather than in the past in order to achieve its global strategies. Turkey follows a policy which is consistent with the global strategy of USA that

⁶ Zekeriya Kurşun Türkiye’nin Ortadoğu ve Afrika’ya Bakışı <http://www.ordaf.org/turkiyenin-ortadogu-ve-afrikaya-bakisi/> Accession Date 12. 09. 2014

⁷ Aybar andOzgoker (2009): “Batı Enerji Güvenliği ve Türkiye”, (Energy Security of the Western World), Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, Sayı: 2, Cilt 11, ss. 319–334.

aims to minimize the dependency of Europe to the Russian natural gas and oil regarding the energy resources as being in Nabucco Pipeline or Southern Flow Corridor.⁸

USA, EU and NATO are still key factors on determining the foreign policy of Turkey, especially toward Middle East. So indeed, Turkish foreign policy is more active than in the past which both is consistent with EU's objectives and is on achieving the new international principles of NATO. Therefore, the "new international existence" of New Turkey doesn't change Turkey's attachment to the Western camp in "new age" and "new geography".

Beyond this, Turkey under the leadership of Ak Party considers that it may adapt the Western values to the Islamic world consistently, and may carry them best by itself to Middle East and other countries. Based on these essentials, the architect of Turkish foreign policy, Prof.Dr. Ahmet Davutođlu, "stylishly" revealed the epistemologic roots of this policy which he built. In his essay published in ForeignPolicy, he formulated this built policy as a foreign policy "that Turkey, which acts so that its historical role and geographical position require as the first decade of twenty first century elapses, builds it on the foundations where the requirements of age are understood very well".

In this sense, he describes the orientation of Turkey toward West and its strategic alliance "as perfectly matching with the peace process of Iraq, Iran, Caucasia and Middle East and with intervention to Afghanistan as well as among others". According to Davutođlu, Turkey "understands" Middle East very well so that it will be very effective there. At the same time, Turkey has a long-term experience associated with the institutional operation of Western values such as market economy and multi-party democracy which may be transmitted by Turkey at the best and will inspire the people in the region.

Those believes helped Davutođlu to formulate the "visionary, consistent, systematic" methodical and operational "strategic depthness" diplomacy principles which "deorbitted" now. At the depth of this strategy, there is "Neo-Ottomanship" which Ak Party executors also frequently mention, but define very clearly.

Davutođlu desired to formulate an Ak Party forign policy strategy which was available between the criteria that there was "a balance between security and democracy" on one hand

⁸ İřeri Emre ve A. Ođuz Dilek (2012), "Yeni Enerji Jeopolitiđinde NATO'nun Enerji Gvenliđinde Tamamlayıcı Rol ve Trkiye'nin Potansiyel Katkıları", (NATO's Complimentary Role in Energy Security and Turkey's Potential Contributions at the New Energy Geopolitics), Akademik Bakıř, Cilt 5, Sayı: 10, s. 229.

and the principle of “zero problem with neighbors” on the other hand in a systematic and consistent methodical approach. As Turkey developed a complimentary relations with other global actors, but not competitive, it aimed to play more active role with a rhythmic diplomacy in the international institutions. Taking place and presiding of Turkey in the North Korea, Afghanistan and Anti-Terrorism Commissions of United Nation’s Security Council in 2010 were shown as the evidence of rhythm of “rhythmic diplomacy”. On the other hand, the events proved that these methodical, operational principles were not defined fully and were weak analytically.⁹

Foreign policy-executers evaluated the “new geography” that the nation-state role would be insufficient to settle the global disputes upon development of globalization under the control of USA.¹⁰ Even though it was recognized that the nation-state had a role to eliminate such threats and to produce the solution in the political, cultural and economic disorders, it was believed that this was transitional.

As the new global order tried to create the mechanisms which it needs, the nation-state “would melt away slowly” within this new formation.¹¹ Turkish foreign policy was formulated with the wide, flexible and ambiguous concepts such as “zero problematic relations with neighbors” around such comments of “new geography”. With own words of Davutoğlu in 2010: “Turkey’s regional policy is based on the security for everybody, high level of political dialog, economic integration and mutual dependency and availability of many cultures together”.

Turkish policy-makers wished to continue to play role in “new geography” primarily by diversifying the foreign policy. As People Republic of China, one of the competitors in Africa, tries to produce the policies toward market-based economy, Turkey “opens to Africa continent”. The severe problems in Caucasia, Balkans and Middle East created the pressure on Turkey to play a regional reconciling role between its strategic alliances and neighbors.

Difficulty to manage such tensions also subject Davutoglu’s foreign policy formulations and aforesaid principles to the test. Concurrently, changing nature of economic

⁹ Davutoğlu Ahmet (2010): “Turkey’s Zero Problems Foreign Policy”, Quoted on 28/08/2012, from http://www.foreignpolicy.com/articles/2010/05/20/turkeys_zero_problems_foreign_policy

¹⁰ Aybar and Ozgoker (2009): “Batı Enerji Güvenliği ve Türkiye”, (Energy Security of the Western World), Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, Sayı: 2, Cilt 11, ss. 319–334.

¹¹ Brzezinski Zbigniew (2008): *America and the World: Conversations on the Future of American Foreign Policy*, Basic Books (Eylül 2008), ISBN 0-465-01501-8.

and politic structure forces the domestic issues and international relations to reconcile.¹² In other words, the established international relations tested the policies which were determined by executive management of Ak Party according to its perception of “current realities of world”, economic, democratic, social and religious setups.

Thus, when the reality of comprehended “new geography” is tested with the concrete events, it is found that they mostly end up with the disappointments. It is possible to follow the fundamental reasons which lie behind the failure of Turkey’s foreign policy in Middle East and their epistemologic built up from the presentation of 2003 objectives which force the government to revise the foreign policy gap and to fill it.

Middle East crisis and Turkish strategy, importance of energy resources and the problems, which are crystallized around the last developments in Syria where the multi-dimension of political developments occurs in the region, impose Turkey under ruling of Ak Party to take position according to “its economic and political interests”, instead of finding the transitional/tactical solutions or solutions around the certain agreements.

Despite the fact that Turkey, itself, develops a warlike discourse, it positions itself based on the “human rights and democracy” which allow the directly efficient military intervention toward Syrian regime to be eliminated.¹³ Turkey’s position against Syria is determined according to the positions of USA and EU that don’t want to see any international armed conflict. This attitude doesn’t want to see that Iran intervenes to the solution of war which is not international within Syria anyway. In addition to them, the rising regional desires of Turkey created the tensions between Turkey and neighbors and furthermore, with existing strategic alliances; this disqualified the efficient zero problem policy - despite of all goodwill. Which lies behind the separatist terrorist campaign that rises with support from Syria and Iran is to express this failure.

As the results of Arab Spring made difficult the idea of Turkish model as “Moderate Islamic Country” which was offered to the “newly emerged democracies”, they also had some negative reflections within the country. Even though the zero problem policy was formulated sincerely with goodwill as others, it did not produce the expected results.

¹²Aybar andOzgoker (2009): “Batı Enerji Güvenliđi ve Türkiye”, (Energy Security of the Western World), Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, Sayı: 2, Cilt 11, ss. 319–334.

¹³İşeri Emre ve A. Oğuz Dilek (2012), “Yeni Enerji Jeopolitiğinde NATO’nun Enerji Güvenliğinde Tamamlayıcı Rolü ve Türkiye’nin Potansiyel Katkıları”, (NATO’sComplimentary Role in Energy Security andTurkey’sPotentialContributions at the New EnergyGeopolitics), Akademik Bakış, Cilt 5, Sayı: 10, s. 229.

As Turkey could not solve the problems, new problems were also added to them. The problems with Armenia is postponed for now. There are deep suspicions and lack of confidence with Iran. The Cyprus problem also began to deeply affect the European Union full membership process of Turkey. The answers to the questions such as what “zero problem” with neighbors and close vicinity or Turkey recently and Turkish trade regarding economy could not be explained completely. It is implied that when it is reached to the “zero problem” status, this will efficiently cease to manage the conflicting interests upon producing the innovative policies.

Growing economy of Turkey required to search the new opportunities in neighboring countries. On the other hand, the developments, having negative impact on economic relations with other countries such as Iraq and Iran, also damage to the relations with Armenia and Syria. In connection with all these, it should also be emphasized the damaging impacts of PKK disturbances in the country.¹⁴

“Neo-Ottomanism” of Turkey toward Middle East and Africa, and new security architecture based on the Greater Middle East Project required Turkey to be interested in African affairs. Ending of Cold War period, immediate after it, Iraq War in 1992 and the developments in Middle East caused Turkey to spread the security emphasis to a wider area, beyond Sahara. New operational plan, which was developed related to sliding of security concerns in 1998, was called as “Policy of Expansion toward Africa”.¹⁵ Hence, when Africa continent started to attract the attention of developing countries such as China and India by beginning of twenty first century, Turkey’s attention also increased toward this continent.

The most important lesson, learnt from analysis of Turkish foreign policy is that the comment on the concept of “new geography” by policy-makers so as ruling the foreign policy doesn’t produce the expected results. This also leads to the inconsistency between the existing resources which are stretched excessively and the determined objectives. Briefly, the miscalculations between the local resources and international ambitions caused the failure of policies.¹⁶

¹⁴Sedat Aybar, Türkiye’nin Ortadoğu Politikası ve Yeni Coğrafya algısı, http://tr.boell.org/sites/default/files/downloads/sedat_aybar_persp.2_tr.pdf Accession Date 20.06.2015

¹⁵Aybar Sedat (2008b): “Türkiye–Afrika İlişkileri”, (Turkey – Africa Relations), Almanak 2007 Analizleri, Sosyal Araştırmaları Vakfı (SAV), s. 353–373

¹⁶İşeri Emre ve A. Oğuz Dilek (2012), “Yeni Enerji Jeopolitiğinde NATO’nun Enerji Güvenliğinde Tamamlayıcı Rolü ve Türkiye’nin Potansiyel Katkıları”, (NATO’s Complimentary Role in Energy Security and Turkey’s Potential Contributions at the New Energy Geopolitics), Akademik Bakış, Cilt 5, Sayı: 10, s. 229.

The realities, ethnical and religious constitution of Middle East, Turkey's strategic position, local economic and political order as well as the complicated water and energy problems made the Turkish foreign policy "insufficient" in order to reconcile the national interests with the continuously changing world. Furthermore, Turkish human and social capital must have been mobilized in order to follow the desired foreign policy objectives. As shown here, the existence of "new geography" parameters made the public support compulsory in order to follow the foreign policy objectives. After AK Party came to power on 3rd November 2002, Turkey began to prioritize Middle East in its foreign policy and showed the desire and tendency toward developing the cooperation with countries in the region in the political, economical and cultural fields as of this period. Turkey, tried to stay away from the crises arose in Middle East during the Cold War period, develops the relations with the countries in region during the last twelve years.

What are the targets behind the normative discourses in Turkish foreign policy toward Arab Spring? The answer of this has been given by the officials again and again, and even though it is known by many of us, those may cause many road accidents, if they may not be explained with the modern political perception and jargon. Because, the emotional approaches toward Arab Spring may cause time to time the perception vulnerability in the addressees.

It is emphasized that the discourses against Turkey are developed due to support that is given to Tunisian government according to the contacts in Tunisia where the Arab Spring started and to the independent resources. In fact, similar situation is also seen in the Egyptian press. An explanation by Mr. Hüseyin Avni Botsalı, the Turkish Ambassador in Egypt, in a meeting was discussed devil a lot in Egyptian press. This crisis, which possibly arose from goodwill explanation or embassy's declaration and mistranslation (the speech text was published in the website of Embassy (<http://cairo.emb.mfa.gov.tr>)), occupied the Egyptian public for a long time. The issue was extended to the intervention to internal affairs and if the news was correct, the Ambassador was invited to the Egyptian Ministry of Foreign Affairs in order to make explanation.

It is natural that each discourse and action of Turkey, which is attached to the region with historical ties and its future interests depend on the cooperation with the region, especiallt with Egypt, may produce the positive and negative echoes in the region. It is unavoidable that they continuously keep Turkey which experiences the similar phases in

confusion and discussions on conflicts of inter-powers that exist in the Arab Spring countries where the great and fast changes are experienced on the agenda.

It is a well-known reality that the army has an impact on politics in Egypt and Tunisia as being in Turkey in the past. Moreover, the army has not directed the politics only, but also has created the employment areas through external aids in Egypt. First of all, it is a disadvantage that Turkey doesn't have an Ambassador who speaks Arabic fluently in a country such as Egypt. If this is not possible, then such important speeches and explanations must be made through the official and reliable translators. At least, the Arabic texts may be distributed together with English versions.

These steps will, of course, not prevent the discussion of Turkey's role in the region today and in the future. This is already expressed by the intellectuals in Egypt and they also emphasize the importance of cooperation with Turkey. However, Turkey's all goodwill and endeavours are wasted, since it may not use the communication tools and especially the language only. Even though we trust the background of our ambassador, Turkey must subject the consuls, consulate chancelleries and of course, the staff of embassies and other staff to a special training as a principle.

It is compulsory that those, who will work in these regions, must be the diplomats who are specialized on the region. This is not so difficult. Each country that desires to be the great power in the world does it and is successful. Do you ever see any US or Russian ambassador who is charged in Turkey and doesn't speak Turkish?¹⁷

The signals on changes in the foreign policy are given with AK Party Government. Özipek states that this change was, in fact, seen during Özal period and is based on the understanding which refuses the approach, "entire world is against us" and introversion.¹⁸ However, the most important point, which differentiates Erdoğan Government from Özal government, is the existence of environment that will support the transformation experienced within Ak Party and will develop a new vision. Likewise, the importance of Prof. Dr. Ahmet Davutoğlu, who has a significant knowledge and background, and provided that the significant developments were experienced during this period, may not be rejected. Davutoğlu

¹⁷Zekeriya Kurşun, Türkiye'nin Temsili Meselesi, <http://www.ordaf.org/turkiyenin-temsili-meselesi/> Accession Date, 3.03. 2013

¹⁸ÖZİPEK, Berat; Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi (AK Parti) Dönemi İç ve Dış Politika (2002-...), Osmanlı'dan 2000'li Yıllara Türkiye'nin Politik Tarihi (iç ve dış politika), Savaş Yayınevi, 2010, ss. 669-690.

mentions that five factors come to forefront as an essential principle of foreign policy which is followed in Turkey: Balance between freedom and security, zero problem with the neighbors, multi-dimensional – multi-track foreign policy, developing a new wording and the idea of which it may not be made concession from freedom based on the principle on establishing connection between the rhythmic diplomacy and security in order to provide the security are adopted.

According to Gürkan Zengin, as all countries worldwide tried to restrict the freedoms against terrorist threat after 11th September attacks, Turkey spent endeavour to widen freedom area ‘without risking the security’. Davutoğlu states how the balance between freedom and security is important as follows: If you make concession from security for freedom, then the chaos occurs; if you make concession from freedom for security, then the authoritarian regimes occur.

Gürkan Zengin explains the principle of zero problem with neighboring countries as follows: The aim in this new approach is to break the chain formed by the enemy rings around us and to make all these fields the security and cooperation areas. Establishing the economic integration zones is considered as the most imperative priority of this principle. Davutoğlu also stated that the developing economic relations between the countries meant minimizing of war risk between them.¹⁹ This principle is constructed upon the psychology of coming though which Turkey is always surrounded with enemies and ‘defensive’ reflex that is developed accordingly, and upon being a country that brings its relations with all neighbors to a good level.

In other words, one may say that creating the mutual economic dependency with border neighbors is an idea which comes to forefront in the Turkish foreign policy. PKK issue is not an internal-sourced problem only at the point that is reached today. Terrorist organization obtains the support from the regions where authority is missing. Turkey tries to develop economic and commercial relations with its neighbors and to support their developments and to prevent said regions to support the terrorism in order to prevent it.

Since the new events are experienced in the international relations day by day, the balances have a potential to change at any moment. In such environment, it is not possible that Turkey implements a region-dependent and static policy. According to Davutoğlu, Turkey should be the country which is not the source of problem but is problem-solving

¹⁹ ZENGİN, Gürkan; Hoca, İnkılap Kitabevi, 2010

country and contributes to the global and regional peace, and should follow a multi-dimensional policy in the various tracks.²⁰ Ahmet Davutođlu adapted the phrase of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, said during Sakarya War, “there is not line defense but area defense, and that area is the entire homeland” to the foreign policy, and said, “there is not line diplomacy but area diplomacy. And that area is the entire world”.

He pointed out that Turkey would carry out the diplomatic activity in this way not only in the region but worldwide. According to Davutođlu, “It should be considered developing the common interest areas with Russia and EU concurrently, establishing the close cooperation with the neighbors and meanwhile, maintaining the strategic relation with USA not a contradiction but the fundamental principle of new policy... Nor our relations with USA are alternative to EU, neither with neighboring countries to USA. In real terms, developing a strategic vision by us depends on which we can see all of them as the factors that complete each other in a big picture”.²¹

Davutođlu sees the relations developed with different countries as not an alternative but factors completing each other in this approach. On the other hand, Turkey assumed the mediator and/or facilitator roles in the solution of these crises during this period. It was asked Davutođlu, “which natural ability do you have?” in an interview by Taraf Newspaper with Davutođlu, and Davutođlu answered that he had “a persuasive ability to stop the parties that were ready for fighting”, and this answer showed how he gave the importance to the mediator role.

As Turkey’s role in the international system was defined, the concept that was frequently used was the role of ‘being a bridge’. However, the function of bridge is to connect two ethnicities each other and to bring one party to the other only; it may not be perceived as an actor which has an independent existence.

Turkey should be defined as ‘center’, not ‘a bridge’ during the new period.²² At this framework, it is emphasized that the new wording must be developed in the Turkish foreign policy. Another important factor is the rhythmic diplomacy. Davutođlu states that he sees the rhythmic diplomacy as a requirement for Turkish foreign policy as follows: “If the conditions

²⁰DAVUTOĐLU, Ahmet; “Türkiye merkez ülke olmalı”, Radikal, 26.02.2004, <http://www.radikal.com.tr/haber.php?haberno=107581> Accession Date: 24.06.2012

²¹ZENGİN, Gürkan; Hoca, İnkılap Kitabevi, 2010

²²DAVUTOĐLU, Ahmet; “Türkiye merkez ülke olmalı”, Radikal, 26.02.2004, <http://www.radikal.com.tr/haber.php?haberno=107581> Accession Date: 24.06.2012

are dynamic and if you stay static, then you may not adjust yourself to such conditions. You should have a diplomacy that continuously moves. So why, I call it rhythmic. That is, even if nothing happens, it should move in site, but must move.²³

Official visits to and meetings in the foreign countries are the evidence of which such diplomacy is implemented. According to Davutođlu, Turkey should not be a bridge, but the center country and should adopt an efficient and dynamic vision consistent with the structure of changing international system in the foreign policy. According to Davutođlu, Turkey could not show its power sufficiently due to the terrorism, political and economical instabilities during 90's. However, at the point that is reached today, Turkey considers the experienced crises as chess and plays the correct chess pieces timely and tends to solve the crises.

The crises that are experienced may be more than one, but all of them are connected to each other. Therefore, the step, which will be taken for one, may bring the solution for other. At this framework, Turkey's Middle East policy was also shaped. Zengin expresses the fundamental steps of new Middle East policy of Turkey as follows: "Objecting to all isolation applications, creating the mutual economic dependency between the countries and regions, not interrupting the dialogs with all states or non-governmental regional actors under no circumstances, protecting the multi-cultural texture in the region, and therefore, protecting the ethnic and religious diversity".²⁴

What is aimed at this framework is to make contribution to the regional peace and security. Abdullah Gl also points out establishing the regional peace and security as the most important condition of economic and social development, saying "any region or any country may not achieve the economic and social development, provide the peace to its people and allow the people to live in welfare without establishing the safe environment and eliminating the enmity around it".

Turkey tried to solve the problems by getting the bottom of problems with the social, cultural, economic, political and diplomatic initiatives, instead of following mostly the security-weighted road map in its foreign policy toward the region. Otherwise, there is a possibility that Turkey may transform to one of the region's instability factors and may be drawn into the complicated problems of region and may increase the threats and problems in

²³ ZENGİN, Grkan; Hoca, İnkılap Kitabevi, 2010

²⁴ ZENGİN, Grkan; Hoca, İnkılap Kitabevi, 2010

its perspective. One of the reasons, which push Turkey to follow such foreign policy, is the economic development.²⁵

After AK Party came to power, Turkish economy gained a great momentum. Today, Turkish economy is shown among the important economies of the world and becomes the attraction center for the investments with foreign capital. Growing economy began to open to the foreign countries through AK Party Government, and the export rates began to rise fast. Today, Turkish economy needs the new markets. This requires Turkey to mend its fences with neighboring countries in a sense and shapes the Middle East policy.

Since the beginning of 21st century, Turkish foreign policy has undergone an important transformation. The public opinion appears to us as an important parameter depending on the understanding of “multi-directional foreign policy” in the foreign policy. Turkey’s geopolitical importance is explained with the new paradigms. As the course of Turkish foreign policy was defined by some people as muddling-through immediate after the Cold War, coming AK Party to power and directing the foreign policy by Ahmet Davutođlu through first, counselling and then, ministry started a new movement in Turkish foreign policy. As this movement was theoretically based on the strategic depth approach of Davutođlu, it defined Turkey as a center country beyond being a bridge. Since said new movement took the strategies of multi-directional foreign policy and zero problem with neighbors as basis, Turkey accelerated its economic and political initiatives instead of West-indexed policies in the regions such as Middle East, Caucasia and Central Asia. In particular, the policies toward Middle East caused the critics that Turkey entered to a tendency toward being Middle Eastern in foreign policy.

New movement in Turkish foreign policy may be considered as a result of transformation at the international system level or as the reflection of values of the AK Party’s leading staff. There are many works on this subject recently.

The foreign policy-internal policy connection, which particularly gained importance with the issue in Davos, has an instrumental significance in terms of which AK Party maintains the public support at a certain level during the economic crisis and gains the sympathy of large masses bespeaking on national feelings. According to Öniş, the foreign policy attack of AK Party is mostly consistent with the public choices and means the process

²⁵ CEYLAN A. ve USLU İ.; “1 Mart Tezkeresinin Türk Dış Politikasına Etkisi”, Uluslararası Politika Akademisi, 15.06.2012, <http://politikaakademisi.org/?p=1118> Accession Date: 31. 07.2012 s.150-159

of which internal policy and foreign policy intertwine. However, it should be emphasized that this relation is not symmetric; in other words, the effecting and determining rate and level of the foreign policy attacks on/of internal policy are not same. In order to understand this situation, the relation, which is neglected, said two dimensions in the formation of Turkish foreign policy must be discussed separately.

It is an ideal attitude that there is a consistency between the citizens' choices and government policies in democracies. If the political leaders take the public choices account when establishing and implementing the policy, then both they meet the requirement of democracy and make the political investment.

In other words, leaders, who would like to strengthen their powers during the democratic process, must take the public choices and tendencies account. Considering the the politics is a game which is played simultaneously at the national and international levels in the today's globalized world, the importance of foreign policy-internal policy connection and in this context, of the public choices may be understood better. Due to this importance, determining the public choices and tendencies, and determining the attitudes toward the current policies will provide the significant clues about the relation between them. As the empirical research is carried out in this paper, no method is implemented in order to measure and evaluate the perceptions related to each foreign policy choice, strategy and concept (e.g. "rhythmic diplomacy", "strategic depth" etc.).²⁶ Rather, it is aimed to examine the attitudes of Turkish people toward Turkis foreign policy.

It began to occur new balances upon invasion of Iraq in Middle East in 2003. After 11th September attacks, the wording and actions of USA in Middle East policy also worried Turkey as many countries in the region. After 2001, Turkey understood that it might not get rid of problems with the approach, "staying away from Middle East problems" which was Turkey's traditional policy. More importantly, the anti-war movement became the general opinion both in the public and elites, and the perception of imperialist West, which tried to divide and manage Middle East for its goals, revived. For this reason, Turkey thought that it would minimize the risk with the solution suggestions for the problems and peaceable policies, not voiding the regional problems.

²⁶ZENGİN, Gürkan; Hoca, İnkılap Kitabevi, 2010

After rejection of resolution which would facilitate the USA's work in TGNA, failure of USA in Iraq led to a power gap in Middle East. Some regional countries such as Turkey and Iran and the global powers tried to fill this gap in line with their economic and political interests. In one sense, it is an unavoidable situation for Turkish foreign policy. Because, it should be considered that Turkey, which is located in an restless and instable region such as Middle East, will be affected by these circumstances. The geopolitic competition on the region unavoidably draws this region and Turkey, country in the region into the process, and forces Turkey to take some steps. Even though the movement, strating during Özal period, left its place to the instability in foreign policy during 1990s, we saw that Turkey gave the first signals of an active policy in Middle East before AK Party. Increasing cooperation between Turkey and Iran, and Turkey and Syria is the evidence of which Turkey follows an active regional policy in an environment where especially, the approach of USA toward Iran and Syria is becoming hard and the international tension increases.

The executive elit in Turkey has thought that Changing Rhetoric and Internal Policy-Foreign Policy relation in the Middle East Policy and all relations to be established with Middle East would damage to the Turkey's Western character and would mean that it would be returning from Republic and modernizing project during the History of Republic. Despite of the Western-centric policies, Turkey came close to the Middle East countries and tried to obtain their support time to time as a result of problems experienced with West during the Cold War period; but Middle East was never seen as an alternative to be oriented.

The process, which the historical, social and economic ties in Middle East were mobilized or it was tried to be mobilized, accelerated with changing of power after 2002 elections. In fact, new Middle East strategy, starting with AK Party, may be considered as the new dimensioned and accelerated status of transformation which its signs were seen in Turkish foreign policy during 1990s. This new process changed both structure and wording of Turkey's policy toward the region. In the structural aspect, Turkey exists in the region by adopting a solution-focused approach, not staying away from the regional problems. In addition to it, Turkey's diplomatic language in Middle East policy also changed. The concepts such as cooperation, integration, development, partnership gained weight.

The foreign policy, which was open to everything, every problem and everybody in a style, "Let's talk", was implemented. It is possible to say that a local style, a "Turkish, Anatolian style" was reflected to the foreign policy. This new rhetoric/style is not limited with

these concepts only, but is developed with other concepts such as a country “producing security”, “strategic depth”, and transforms to the application-based new policies at the framework of these concepts.

Davutoğlu states that the fundamental principles of this approach are balance between the security and freedom, zero problem with the neighbors, developing the relations with the neighboring countries beyond existing one, multi-directional foreign policy and the rhythmic diplomacy. The biases related to Turkey were eliminated at the certain level with the newly shaped Turkish foreign policy around these concepts and the traditional relations in the region changed at the certain level. Turkey is already a country which is taken account. In the cases of crisis, Turkey’s mediation is sought and the solutions are produced with the contribution from Turkey. The states, enemies of each other, come together under the supervision of Turkey.

If it is necessary to summarize this new foreign policy regarding the period, then one may say that Turkey is passive by the beginning of 2000’s, active after 2003 and starts to realize proactively its economic and politic interests in Middle East during the post-2006 period under the effect of changes in the regional and global systems. The persons/institutions, involving in this process, affect the political structure and public opinion results as making selection/deciding among some alternatives in the foreign policy. Fundamentally, these are handled in two categories in general terms: internal environment and external environment. External environment is the structure of international system, interests of other states or regional and international power distribution. Internal environment includes the political structure of country, government type, and the qualifications of public opinion and decision-makers.

It is known that different factors are effective on Turkish foreign policy during AK Party period. According to Kardaş, the foreign policy of AK Party is the product of four different variables. Those are listed as changes in the power balance and at the system level, changes in the internal policy, identity and finally, public tendencies. One may say that Ak Party, which came to power in 2002 and was elected by the people in four elections including the next local elections, considered, especially the systemic effects and international conjuncture in foreign policy options, and did not disregard the expectations of voters, even gave priority to them. The most important point, which must be emphasized, is that the people’s expectations and demands must be taken account by the governments in

democracies, and the manner of reflection of this to the foreign policy and how it is perceived in the region where this policy is directed to and how it is responded. Taking the public tendencies account in the foreign policy is a fact which will be meaningful in the democratic systems.

As long as the democratizing and political participation increase, the voters' tendencies and choices gain importance. The connection of political power-voter choices is important in the foreign policy options, especially as a requirement of principle of executives' democratic responsibility. The works, carried out in USA, show that public has the consistent and rationalist attitudes toward the foreign policy. The fact, which Ziya Öniş, the lecturer in Koç University, called as democratizing of foreign policy, points out that the civil society apparently participates in the foreign policy moves gradually and the importance of public tendencies increases in the decisions related to foreign policy.

Public opinion-foreign policy connection, which especially gained importance during the second ruling period of AK Party, may be perceived as a result of said democratization. It would be true to say that these recent developments also affect the image of Turkey abroad. For example, Süleyman Demirel, who represented the bureaucratic-statist structure rather than an expectation which was democratic and the social recognition level was low in 1997, had to leave the summit of Islamic Conference Organization (ICO) where Turkish foreign policy was criticized harshly.

The tradition, which Süleyman Demirel represented, had to leave the scene of Turkish political life in the later years. Whereas, in 2003, even though Abdullah Gül, the Minister of Foreign Affairs, criticized the human rights, democracy and woman rights in his speech during the summit of same organization, everybody warmly applauded him. Similarly, the Libyan visit, which was made by Necmettin Erbakan during the years when he was in power and was entertained in the tent, was not welcomed by the public and had the very serious reactions. However, both the visiting by the Prime Minister Erdoğan in the same country about after ten years was welcomed by the public and he was entertained by Kaddafi at the top-end level and the warm welcome was shown to him. This gives the clue about the effect of changing internal dynamics, on one hand and about the importance of manner of the perception by foreign public, on the other hand.

In this context, the research, executed in the countries in region, shows that the changing policies of Turkey come to attention in the region. It is clearly seen that the support,

given to Turkey's mediator role in the problems within the region and to which it plays more active role in Arab world, is very high. Furthermore, it shows that more than three fourth of participants of study believe that Turkey would have a positive contribution to establish the peace in Arab world and at this point, they perceived the Turkey's closeness to the region as an advantage.

The factors such as rejection of 1st March resolution, developments in Turkey-EU relations, reaction of Turkey toward Gaza attacks and Davos event and representing by Turkey a Middle West vision, which was democratic, stable, peaceful, and had higher welfare and capacity to solve the problems itself, were played a significant role on establishing the positive image of Turkey.

It should be remembered that Turkey is a country which modernization process is mostly completed, has taken the important steps toward strengthening the democracy and has a liberal economy and that those factors shape the Turkey's foreign policy options in order to understand better the foreign policy-internal policy relation and the public opinion role in shaping this relation. Since the foreign policy will occur as a result of interaction of the very different environments each other in the democratic and economic structure having these features, it will have a greater legitimacy basis. One may say that as long as the dynamics within a country change, the foreign policy would be evolved in this direction.

Prof.Dr. Kemal Kirişçi from Boğaziçi University mentions that the foreign policy of AK Party shows, in fact, consistency with the endeavours of liberalizing the Turkish economy and making the democracy pluralism that are demanded by Turkish society. According to some experts, when Turkey realizes the transformation in its internal policy and the people's demands are reflected to the political plane, Turkey finds its potential and begins to evolve from neighboring country toward the center country position in the foreign policy. This opens the way of multi-track, rhythmic diplomacy with zero problem with the neighbors as defined by Davutoğlu. Considering the possibility of or existing relation between Middle East countries and Turkey as requirement and obtaining the clear support from the public depend on occurring of psychology toward this objective. However, it will not be true to say that these public support and expectations affect sufficiently the decisions of decision-makers.

Since studying how they evaluated the movement occurring in the Turkish foreign policy after 2000s would show whether or not the educated and young people in the society would support the foreign policy of government, it would be an important finding for the

government. Since the youngsters, generally forming 18-24 age range, form the electorate who mostly complete the political socialization during the period of new foreign policy movement, determining the perception of aforesaid people toward the strategies related to the foreign policy and Middle East would clear up the positive and negative reactions about the AK Party policies throughout the community.

If it is remembered the leadership role that was played by the educated and young people in the public civil commotions occurred in the various regions of Middle East during early 2011, the importance of understanding the attitude of the young people regarding the managing of foreign policy's future and recognition of such policies. A survey study was executed with the students of Cumhuriyet University in order to measure the Method and Sampling Youngsters' perception about foreign policy and attitude about the movement toward Middle East. In order to complete the survey fast and efficiently, all of the questions were transferred to the computer via software which was issued within the scope of project. Total 800 students from the different departments of the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences and from other faculties participated in the survey. As the students were selected, the sampling was formed according to the convenience method. As the sampling was formed, the attention was paid to select the students from the different faculties of university.

As the computerized survey application facilitated to obtain the higher completion percentage, the questions, which appeared one by one on the screen, allowed the participants to answer them without being bored. Even though the sampling was formed according to the convenience method, it may be said that the sampling was obtained which representation qualification was high according to the sex, faculty and socio-economic state criteria. Cumhuriyet University, which was an education institution that the students from different groups throughout Turkey preferred due to the city's location where the university was situated, was effective on obtaining the sampling that its representative power was high.

When the foreign policy objectives come into question in contrary to the foreign policy's priorities, the significant part of those, who participate in the survey, emphasize that Turkey should play the leadership role in Middle East and Balkans. For instance, as 73% out of participants acknowledge the target that Turkey should be the leader country in Middle East, this rate becomes 61% for its leadership role in Balkans.

As the rate of those, who acknowledge the target that Turkey should be the leader of Islamic Organization, is 54%, the rate of those, who acknowledge that Turkey should be the member of EU, is 45%. The rate of those, who don't acknowledge the Turkey's EU membership, is quite higher (29%). We find that the rate of those, who support the target of which Turkey establishes the Union with Central Asian countries, is 57%.

When the data is evaluated, it is found that the university youth have a multi-directional attitude about foreign policy's priorities and put the foreign policy objectives to be followed in Middle East, Balkans, Islamic world and Central Asian countries forward the EU membership. Here, achieving a higher rate such as 73% especially on being a leader country in Middle East shows that the foreign policy strategies of the government, which gives priority to Middle East, has also a broad repercussion among the young people. The question that must be asked at this point is whether their attitudes related to the identity and values play the role on appearance of those choices.

The attitudes of young people, who form the young, educated and dynamic substrate of public about the foreign policy, were studied. The perceptions on the foreign policy and strategy that was followed by the government in Middle East were shown with a survey study which was executed on 800 students and it might be assumed that its representation power was higher.

Turkish foreign policy gained a new direction within the international system which changed during 2000s. It was moved away from the rhetoric of which the country was surrounded with enemies on four sides during the AK Party period, and it was implemented a foreign policy which was active, multi-directional and zero problem with neighbors. One of the areas of foreign policy movement, which gained speed during the second period of AK Party, was Middle East.

The new direction of Turkey that changed its direction toward West due to the security concern starting from the last periods of Ottoman and then, aimed to be the member of EU was called by some as axial dislocation or 'Being Middle Eastern' of Turkish foreign policy. Against such criticisms, the governmental officials said that there were not such axial dislocation and direction change, but Turkey followed a multi-directional and active foreign policy.

Both movement in the foreign policy and the discussions about this subject became one of the agenda items of public. In particular, Davos crisis and attack to Mavi Marmara showed that the foreign policy-internal policy relation gained importance and the political parties considered it as an instrument which might affect the voters' choices. This may be, in fact, interpreted as a natural result of conflict between the new strategies which are summarized with the principle of 'Peace at Home, Peace in the World' in foreign policy and are developed against the Western-centered foreign policy.

This fault line in the foreign policy led to a case that made the citizens' choices the determinative dynamic beyond being the monitoring factor of foreign policy and was called as the democratization of foreign policy. Survey results showed that the university youth that formed the youngest and most dynamic group of voters had the critical and multi-directional attitudes related to the foreign policy.

As 37% out of youngsters stated that the foreign policy strategy of current government was correct, 31% of them found this strategy wrong. However, despite of this critical tone, 57% of them stated that the foreign policy strategy of government was in favor of the country.

In the study, as the rate of those, who determined the identity of Turkey as 'Turkish' in the foreign policy, was found 47%, there was not any correlation between perceptions of participants related to the Turkey's identity in the foreign policy and the support given to the foreign policy strategies of government according to the obtained data. Especially, in contrary to the criticisms that the foreign policy became Middle Eastern and AK Party found a base on this direction, it was found that the attitudes giving priority to Middle East and Islamic World or identity perceptions were not very important.

According to the result of survey, it was found that as the significant part of youngsters saw the Turkey's future in EU and Turkic Republics (total rate 66%), the rate of those, who found the future in Middle East, was 13%. Considering the rate of those who find the Turkey's future in Islamic World (17%), it is found that the criticisms, suggested by some experts and groups on axial dislocation and being Middle Eastern in the foreign policy, are not valid for the attitudes of educated youngsters.

According to the results of survey, one may say that the university youth is open to the different alternatives in the Turkish foreign policy and is the supporter of foreign policy

options toward the different regions and generally supports the government's strategies. It may be concluded that this support is conditional and the youngsters consider the 'Turkish' identity as the basis in foreign policy, prioritize EU and Turkic World, but desire that an active foreign policy should be followed in Islamic World and Middle East. Finally, according to the survey results, it may be concluded that the attitudes of youngsters related to the foreign policy objectives and to the foreign policy strategies that the government must follow are generally consistent. Despite of this, when this finding is evaluated with the results which are stated above and related to the support given to the foreign policy, foreign policy objectives and perceptions, it may be said that the educated youngsters don't give the support without condition.

When it is considered that the similar tendencies may also be valid for a wider public opinion, the policy-makers and executors must take them into account when directing the strategies. As requirement of the principle of democratic responsibility, it may easily be suggested that as the foreign policies toward Middle East or another region are determined, the public may exercise the power that they have in the elections; in this context, taking the preferences and attitudes of both university youth, who are the most active and educated group of public and public in a wider sense into account, would be a rational strategy.

CHAPTER 1

1. MIDDLE EAST PERCEPTION IN TURKEY / TURKEY PERCEPTION IN MIDDLE EAST BEFORE 2002

Two fundamental characteristics of Turkish Foreign Policy have come into the forefront since establishment of the Republic of Turkey:

1) Status Quoism,

2) Westernism.

The status quoism, which is one of the aforesaid two characteristics of Turkish Foreign Policy, is defined as protecting the existing borders and maintaining the existing balances. Briefly, maintaining the order, which was established at the end of the First World War, appears as the first aim.

Westernism, the second characteristic of Turkish Foreign Policy, doesn't mean the geographical area, but emphasizes the Western economics, science and civilization.²⁷ In order to fully understand the Middle East perception of Turkey, it would be beneficial to categorize the period from 1923 to today into the certain periods taking account the followed policies; period between 1923-1950; 1950-1960; 1960-1983; 1983-1993; 1993-2002; and post-2002 Ak Party period...

1.1 Mutual “others perception” between 1923-1950:

During the first years of this period, the political geography of Middle East was not shaped completely. During the First World War, the Arabs moved with the idea to establish their independent states. At the end of war, Arabs got rid of the Ottoman State, but could not gain their independence.

Arabs only got rid of the Ottoman, but instead, faced with their Christian masters.²⁸ In general, during this period which covers the first years of the Republic of Turkey, it is stated that the relations with Middle East completely broke down and even, new Turkish government did not establish the relation with the Arabs willingly. Arabic Middle East

²⁷ Baskın Oran, “Türk Dış Politikasının Teori ve Pratiği”, Baskın Oran (ed.), Türk Dış Politikası Kurtuluş Savaşından Bugüne Olgular, Belgeler, Yorumlar, Cilt 1, İstanbul, İletişim Yayınları, 2001, ss. 46-53.

²⁸ Memoirs of AgaKhan, Londra, 1954, s.153-154. aktaran, Peter Mansfield, Osmanlı Sonrası Türkiye ve Arap Dünyası, Söylem yayınları, İstanbul, 2000, s. 80.

struggled for its independence until the years of the Second World War. In such circumstance, it would not be rational to think that Turkey intervened to the regional problems. Of course, during this period, the endeavors of Arabs to create the nation-state even under the mandate system, and intitations by newly emerged states to create the new identity as well as pursuing both by new Turkish state and Arabs modernization prevented the development of establishing the cooperation/development of relations between the region countries.

In building of new indetities, the “others” image is generally effective. States, emerged in Arabic Middle East emphasized their Turkish past as “others” in creation of their new identities. New Turkish state also saw the Arabs as “others” time to time.²⁹ Briefly, during this period, extension of independence war that emerged in Arabic Middle East at the end of the First World War until the Second World War, namely, not finalization of political geography of the region and in general, gaining the security issues weight prevented the development of relations between Turkey and Arabic Middle East.

1.2. Years of 1950-1960 Baghdad Pact and mutual “negative perceptions”:

1950s were the years when Turkish Foreign Policy became distant from the Arabic Middle East. Exaggerated and outrageous use of “Westernism”, one of two fundamental characteristics of the Turkish Foreign Policy during these years, moved Turkey away from the region and significantly tarnished the Turkey’s image in the eyes of Arabs in the region. It is found that Turkey, which followed a policy that was defined as “active partisanship” during 1950s, acted as if it was the representative of West in the region.

Considering the significant events occurring in Middle East during said years, it is observed that Turkey implements an exaggerative Western-oriented policy. Upon UK and France lost their efficiency that they had in the past after the Second World War, and USA and Soviet Union emerged as the new powers, they led to emerging of a new system in the international policy. In the new order which is known as Bipolar System, the regions, where the conflicts were densely occurred between two blocks, were Europe and Middle East.

Turkey tried to secure itself by taking place in the Western Block as a country in the region and with the effect of threatening from Soviet Union. Turkey implemented a fully “Western-oriented” policy with Security concerns in order to take place in the political,

²⁹Araplar ve Türklerin birbirleri hakkındaki yanlış algılamalar için bkz: Oya AkgöneçMughisuddin, TurkeyandtheMiddle East: SystemicandSubsystemicDeterminants of Policy 1960-1975, ForeignPolicyInstitute, Ankara, 1993, ss. 67-71.

economic and military institutions of West. As the Turkey's foreign policy against the events in Middle East during 1950s made it come closer to West, especially to USA, it moved Turkey away from Arabs. The events such as establishing of Baghdad Pact, 1956 Suez War, 1957 Syrian Crisis, 1958 Iraqi Coup and 1958 Lebanese Crisis, which were the important events in Middle East during 1950s, left their mark, and Turkey had a Western-oriented attitude during such regional events. Especially in establishing of Baghdad Pact, the attitude of Turkey had a deep negative impact on perception of Arabs on Turkey.

As Turkey aimed to create a security zone against Soviet threatening in favor of West during those years, on the contrary, it contributed to creation of an Anti-Western structure in favor of Soviet Union in Middle East. Briefly, Turkey implemented a policy which was "active", "Westernist" but costly regarding the results in Middle East during 1950s. Upon increasing of impact of the Cold War in the region, Turkey showed clearly its Western-oriented attitude against Soviet Union as a front country with taking position against the events. During this period, one may easily say that Middle East policies of Turkey were used as an instrument and area of its foreign policy toward West.

1.3. 1960-1983 Period

1960s were the years when Turkey began to review the foreign policy. During said period, it is observed that there were changes in Turkey's attitude toward the events occurred in Middle East. This change in the Turkey's policy toward the region completely occurred depending on the course of relations with West. For instance, Turkey needed to review the policy toward Middle East due to the disturbance/disappointment for the Western attitude about Cyprus Issue.

At this framework, the problems, experienced with West related to the Cyprus issue and in parallel with it, Johnson's Letter, pushed Turkey to change the foreign policy which Turkey implemented toward Middle East especially during 1950s. Turkey, which thought that it neglected Arabs, showed an Arab-oriented attitude in the Middle East issues within the context of this foreign policy change. During 1960-1983, it is a period when the critical approach and closing toward Middle East are started in the Turkish Foreign Policy. 1960s are considered as the relative autonomy period in terms of Turkish Foreign Policy regarding the past. Briefly, the shock with West during 1960s reminded Turkey of Middle East and caused Turkey to create a different viewpoint and approach toward the region.

1.4. 1983-1993 Period

1980s are the years when the security and defense are the determinative issues in the Turkish Foreign Policy. Iran Islamic Revolution in 1979 had a significant impact on Turkey's policy toward Middle East. During that period, Turkey implemented a Western-oriented policy, again. Furthermore, Iran Islamic Revolution also caused assigning of an ideologic meaning to Turkey's policy toward Middle East.

Except development in Iran, the issues such as terror and water problem were determinant in the Turkey's viewpoint toward the region regarding the Turkey's Middle East policy. Briefly, that period was the years when security issues made feel their weights in the Turkey's foreign policy toward said region.

1.5. 1993-2002 Period

During early of 1990s, ending of Cold War and ending of bipolar world system upon collapsing of Soviet Union and Yugoslavia caused the emergence of new ethic and religious conflicts around Turkey. During that period, the assays were published about which Turkey's strategic importance decreased regarding West.

Emerging of new security issues in such environment, where it was discussed how the Western alliance was beneficial, caused the Turkey's security issue into forefront in its Middle East policies. Gaining the security issues weight and arising those issues mostly from the Arabic countries such as Syria and Iraq led to the development of Turkey-Israel relations.

As Turkey's security-oriented viewpoint toward Middle East caused the emergence of Turkish-Israeli strategic partnership during 1990s, it was understood as Turkey moved away from the Arabic world and caused that Turkey was seriously criticized by Arabic world.³⁰

When one looks at from this angle, it is seen the similarities in Turkey's view on Middle East between 1950s and 1990s. As stated before, as Turkey, which approached to the region in the West/USA perspective during 1950s, moved away from Middle East, it established a strategic partnership with Israel during 1990s and tended to move away from

³⁰ For further information about development and status of Turkish-Israeli relations during 1990s, see: OfraBengio, *Türkiye-İsrail: Hayalet İttifaktan Stratejik İşbirliğine*, Erguvan Yayınevi, İstanbul, 2009, Türel Yılmaz, *Türk-İsrail Yakınlaşması*, İmaj Yayıncılık, Ankara, 2001, Süha Bölükbaşı, "Türkiye ve İsrail: Mesafeli Yakınlıktan Stratejik Ortaklığa", aban H. Çalış-İhsan D. Dağı-Ramazan Gözen (Eds.), *Türkiye'nin Dış Politika Gündemi Kimlik, Demokrasi, Güvenlik, Liberte Yayınları*, 2001.

Arab world again. As understood from this case, maintaining the relations of Turkey with the region via security issues plays a role which minimizes the efficiency of Turkey in the region and when the security issues gain weight, the development is found in the relations with USA and Israel, and moved away from the region/Arabs.³¹

2000 and Beyond; even though the change/development in policy of Turkey toward Middle East occurs from early 2000s, the milestone of said change in the policy of Turkey toward the region may be considered as 1998. Despite the fact that it assumed an active role and even subjected to the big damages in the international coalition which USA led during the First Gulf War in 1991, as it was not considered sufficiently by USA at the end of USA, EU rejected the Turkey's membership in 1997.

Under these negative circumstances, Adana Agreement, which was concluded between Turkey and Syria in 1998, opened the door to Middle East again. The security issues, which Turkey faced during 1990s, and not finding the support from West in such issues led Turkey to review its foreign policy in general and Middle East policy in private. After the terrorist attacks to the World Trade Center and Pentagon on September 11th, 2001, the discourse and action of US foreign policy toward Middle East also caused the worry in Turkey as well as in many countries in the region.

After 2001, Turkey understood that it would not get rid of the problems with the traditional policy, "staying away from Middle East issues". Thereafter, Turkey considered that it would minimize the risk with eirenicons related to the issues and peaceable policies, not intervening to the regional issues. Following developments from the early 2000s led Turkey to orient to Middle East.

1- Due to the double standard policies of European Union toward Turkey, not maintaining the EU membership process of Turkey well.

2- Confidence crisis in Turkey-US relations upon invasion of Iraq by US in 2003.

3- Diminishing of economic attraction of EU and old Soviet Russian geography together with the economic crisis throughout the world in 2009.

³¹For further information about Turkish-Arabian relations from old ages to 2000s, see: İki Taraf Açısından Türk-Arap Münasebetleri, İslam, Tarih, Sanat ve Kültür Araştırma Merkezi (IRCICA) Yayınları, İstanbul, 2000.

CHAPTER 2

1. CHANGING PERCEPTION BETWEEN TURKEY-IRAN AFTER 2002

In order to understand this period and to foresee the changing perceptions, it should be remembered the brief history of Turkey-Iran relations. The basis of Turkey-Iran relations is very old. Safavids (the Persian community) from the same generation existed in the region that was Iranian geography today by early 1500s...

Turkey, one of those two states which have not been in close relation from the establishment of Republic of Turkey until 1950s, established the Baghdad Pact aiming to surround USSR and known as Green Zone with UK and Iran upon obtaining the support from US and UK against the possibility of which USSR might spread its ideology throughout the world by early years of cold war in 1955. After Iran Islamic Revolution in 1979, Iran completely moved away from the Westernist line and became a country which implemented the anti-Western policies.

Iran, supporting the PKK terrorist organization against Turkey during 1990s, clearly showed its disturbance about relation of Turkey with Israel. Furthermore, it may be said that those relations make Iran come closer to Syria rather than to Turkey.³² At the same time, as this expresses the viewpoint of Iranian State toward Turkey, it may be determined that Iranian perception about Turkey is not friendly during such years.

After AK Party came to power on November 3rd, 2002, Turkey began to give priority to Middle East in the foreign policy and showed desire and tendency to develop a cooperation in the political, economic and cultural areas with the countries in the region as of that period. It is found that Turkey, which tried to stay away from the crises as much as possible in Middle East during the Cold War, has given importance to the relations with the countries in region during the last decade. One of the events, which are attracted the attention of international community during that period, is the Turkish-Iranian convergence.

In 2012, the Agreement on Common Use of Kapıköy and Razi Land Entry Points, and again, the Agreement on Common Use of Esendere and Sero Land Entry Points were concluded by and between Government of Turkish Republic and Iran Islamic Republic.³³ It is

³²Baskın Oran, Türk Dış Politikası, İletişim Yayınları İstanbul 2010, C.II, s.580

³³<http://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/default.aspx>

observed that those agreements make the relations between the countries, being parties of them, warmer both in the commercial and political manners. In this context, the parties agreed upon providing the common service in order to facilitate the international passenger, good and vehicle traffics and to facilitate the border entry and customs procedures without repeating at Kapıköy and Razi Land Entry Points at the framework of provisions of the Memorandum of Understanding in the agreement concluded for use of border posts.³⁴

Beko, which is one of the leading companies of Turkey and aims to grow in export, organized the last dealers meeting upon participation of 900 authorized dealers in Tehran, the capital city of Iran in 2005. Beko announced that it aimed to strengthen its position among the brands which the consumers in Iran liked and preferred, and to increase the market share in the country. Arçelik A.Ş., operating under Beko brand in Iran, obtained US\$ 4.2 billion turnover during the first eight months of 2005. Arçelik, Beko had 160 thousand products met the Iranian consumers until 2005. Aka Gündüz Özdemir, the general manager of Arçelik, said in his speech during the dealers meeting, "44 percent of our turnover in 2004 was from sales abroad, and most of those sales were made under the Beko brand." This may be considered as one of the important examples of process which is created with Iran in trade.³⁵

As Gürcan Karakaş, the General Manager of Bosch Industry under Bosch Group said that they would make investment beyond Euro 105 million in Turkey in 2005, he also stated that they worked in order to open to Iran via Turkey. Karakaş, who told the 2005 objectives of company, mentioned that they increased the operation fields and investments gradually in every year, and became one of the biggest foreign investors in Turkey.

Karakaş, who said that Bosch Group gained Euro 1.5 billion and Bosch Industry Euro 487 million in Turkey last year, stated that the turnover target of Bosch Industry this year was beyond Euro 500 million. Karakaş, who said that the company has also assumed the responsibility of Iran as well as of Turkey since 2003 and carried out the works in order to bring its achievements there, carried out works for Iran that was the biggest market following China in automotive. Karakaş said that they considered Iran as a big potential with 1 million of vehicle production annually and average 20 percent of growing market every year, and the tender related to Turkcell, which has caused an economic crisis for a long time with Iran, was greatly concluded in 2005.

³⁴Agreement on Common Use of Kapıköy and Razi Land Entry Points by and between Government of Turkish Republic and Iran Islamic Republic

³⁵Türkiye-İran ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

The license was issued to Irancell consortium which planned to be the first private company in Iranian mobile phone market as the second GSM operator, and it was notified that Turkcell, which had the most of shares in consortium, must have transferred the guarantee amount that it must have paid until 4th September. In the announcement from Iranian Ministry of Information and Technology, it mentioned that the license was issued to Irancell upon the local companies were involved in the consortium following the long-term negotiations and the meeting was organized with the executives of local companies upon participation of the Ministr Ahmed Mutemidi in order that the second mobile phone operator in Iran began to work, and in the declaration after this meeting, it was stated that it was decided to transfer 21 percent share of Turkcell to National Bank and Post Bank.³⁶

In the declaration which was emphasized that it was provided the time to Turkcell which had the majority of shares in Irancell project until 4th September in order to transfer the guarantee which it must have paid, If Turkcell fails to fulfill its obligations, then MTN, the South African company, which quoted the second higher price in the tender, would be substituted with Turkcell and in the explanation, it was stated that it was expected that Turkcell would not create any problem about participation in the project after the negotiations with company officials. Consortium under the leadership of Turkcell was awarded the contract on mobile phone license on February 2004, but the conservative deputies in Iranian Assembly dropped the Turkcell's shares in Irancell agreement from 70 percent to 49 percent. Despite the fact that Turkcell's shares were dropped in Irancell consortium, Turkcell announced that it accepted the conditions and would participate in the project.³⁷

After the tender held on February 2004, it was decided that Turkcell would pay Euro 300 million of license fee. It was considered that after starting operation by the second GSM operator, up to 11 million users would be added to about 6 million of registered mobile phone user in Iran where only one mobile phone operator operated within three years.

Pursuant to the Agreement on Natural Gas Purchasing Selling that was signed with Russia for 25-year term, it is aimed to reach to 16 million m³ with gradual increasing in natural gas delivery during 2007; natural gas will flow about 12 million m³ during the first months, will flow 2 billion m³ increasing by the time during the first year. Even though this figure was stated as 4 billion m³ in the contract, since use of gas diminished due to economic

³⁶Mehmet TAN ve Pelin ALİYEV, 2002 Sonrası Türk Dış Politikası Bağlamında Türkiye İnan İlişkilerinin Değerlendirilmesi.

³⁷Türkiye-İnan ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

crisis in Turkey and not installing the new distribution lines, it was decreased to 2 billion m3 for the first year.³⁸

No decreasing was demanded in the amount of natural gas to be purchased from Iran under this project. However, the officials from the Ministry of Energy, who would like to readjust the natural gas prices, stated that since Iran did not accept the price discount during the longer negotiations, no result was obtained and therefore, it must have been applied to the International Arbitration. According to data from BOTAŞ, Turkey should purchase 6.689 billion m3 of natural gas from Iran pursuant to the agreement between two countries. It was aimed to increase the amount of natural gas to be purchased from Iran about to 10 billion m3 annually from 2007.

The second project was the official opening of Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan Crude Oil Pipeline. Lord Browne, the Chairman of BP (British Petroleum), opened the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan Crude Oil Pipeline officially by the participation of Ilham Aliyev, the President of Republic of Azerbaijan, Samuel Bodman, the US Minister of Energy and Mihail Saakasvili, the President of Republic of Georgia and Ahmet Necdet Sezer, the President of Republic of Turkey on 25th June 2005. The project was initiated with the signing of agreement on 20th September 1994.

Deceased State President of Azerbaijan, Haydar Aliyev, who was one of the leaders offering the project, announced BTC as “the foundation of new oil strategy of Azerbaijan.” USA spent too much endeavour in order to realize this project. However, Russian Federation discountenanced this project being anxious about which it would decrease the energy exportation of country.

BTC pipeline has a big strategic importance. Transmission of energy resources in Caspian basin to the Western countries is very important both regarding Turkey and countries in the region.³⁹ Pipeline has 50 million tons of transmission capacity annually. Advantage of this project regardin Turkey is to minimize the oil transport in the Turkish straits.

Some important steps were taken in security between Turkey and Iran in 2005. On the other hand, it was informed that 3 PKK terrorists, whom were captured in the border on Iran

³⁸KARACASULU, Nilüfer; "Türk Dış Politikasında İran", *Uluslararası IV. Türk Dış Politikası Sempozyum Tebliğleri: Yeni Dönemde Türk Dış Politikası*, Ed. Osman B. Dinçer ve öte., Ankara, USAK (Uluslararası Stratejik Araştırmalar Kurumu), Şubat 2010, ss. 203-219.

³⁹Türkiye-İran ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

side, were delivered to the security forces in Hakkâri, and 1 terrorist surrendered himself, and after the terrorists were questioned, they were taken to the court and arrested. This process may be considered as one of the concrete examples on change in the Iranian perception regarding the Turkey's national security.⁴⁰

Lebanese crisis in Middle East minimized partly the pressure of USA on Iran. Mahmut Ahmedinejad, the President of Republic of Iran, made no concessions from his firm position about the nuclear facilities and rejected rigorously the offers from UK, France and Germany at the beginning of 2006, and Ahmedinejad opened officially the nuclear conversion facility in Esfahan. Six months later, he had the uranium enrichment unit operated in Natanz, again.

According to Ömer Ersun, the retired ambassador, European countries, which have tried to make US be calm on this issue for three years, are already out of patience. However, Iran plans to expand the nuclear issue to a wider area. According to Gülden Ayman, this target is the "Conflict of Civilizations" in one aspect. The words of Ayetullah Hamaney, the Supreme Leader of Iran, are the expression of this target, saying "since the arrogant powers that are managed by USA are afraid of development of Islamic countries, they also object to the scientific and technologic development of Iran" that he spent in the state TV.⁴¹

Summit of Economic Cooperation Organization was held in Baku on 5th May 2006. Prime Minister Erdogan from Turkey and the President of Republic, Mahmud Ahmedinejad from Iran are the important leaders who take place in the summit. The discussion subject of two leaders, who met in this important summit, was the nuclear activities of Iran. The following conversation was made between two leaders: Erdogan said, "We say that we want the diplomatic solution until the end. We pay attention to the issue for stability and peace. You are expected to be more transparent, should eliminate the concerns. No other ways must be searched for solution." Ahmedinejad said: "Iran has been subjected by West to many embargoes since 1979 Islamic Revolution. They assumed that we would knuckle under these pressures and would not be successful, but they were wrong. By the help of Allah, we achieved to enrich the uranium." Erdogan, who continued to speak after these words, offered

⁴⁰ÜZÜMCÜ, Adem; "Türkiye'nin Enerji Güvenliği ve Dış Politika Yansımaları", *Uluslararası IV. Türk Dış Politikası Sempozyum Tebliğleri: Yeni Dönemde Türk Dış Politikası*, Ed. Osman B. Dinçer ve öte., Ankara, USAK (Uluslararası Stratejik Araştırmalar Kurumu), Şubat 2010, ss. 171-202

⁴¹Türkiye-İran ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

to Ahmedinecad: We have a very bad example of Iraq in our region. Middle East doesn't have any other tolerance toward a new instability.⁴²

During visit by our Prime Minister, Mr. Recep Tayyip Erdogan in Tehran between 28-29 January 2014, Preferential Trade Agreement, which have been negotiated between Turkey and Iran for a decade, was signed by our Minister of Economy, Nihat Zeybekçi and the Iranian Minister of Industry, Mine and Trade, Mr. Muhammed Rıza Nematzade before the Prime Ministers of two countries.⁴³ It was agreed upon which Turkey would provide the tariff discount in some agriculture products to Iran and against this, Iran would provide the tariff discount in some industrial products to Turkey through Turkish-Iranian Preferential Trade Agreement.

Among the products which Iran would provide the tariff discount to Turkey through Preferential Trade Agreement, there are many products such as cleaning agents, drugs, cosmetics, plastic materials, forest products, textile, ready wear, home textile, furniture, steel products, iron and non-ferrous metals, refrigerator, the white goods such as dishwashing machines, air conditioners and electrical-electronic products.

Turkish-Iranian Preferential Trade Agreement is the first agreement about increasing the trade of our country, except the Free Trade Agreements. Turkish-Iranian Preferential Trade Agreement will give acceleration to the economic and commercial relations between two countries, strengthen the economic cooperation between two countries during the new period and will form the foundation of increasing economic cooperation between two countries during the future period. Within the scope of agreement, both countries undertook to work on expanding the concessions that they provided to each other.⁴⁴

Another important subject, which Turkey gives importance and tries to contribute, is the activities which Iranian state carries out in nuclear area. About this subject, the words of Ahmedinecad, who said to international public opinion, are the important expressions which leave their mark on the history: "Nuclear energy may not be under the monopoly of any country. Iran has right about it and we will not allow anyone to prevent it; our program is carried out transparently. UAEK audits our facilities." Again, as the words of Ahmedinecad

⁴²ÖZPEK, Burak Bilgehan; "En Uzun On Yıl: 11 Eylül Sonrası Ortadoğu", *Ortadoğu Etütleri*, Cilt 3, No 2, Ocak 2012, ss. 183-215

⁴³ÇAKIROĞLU, Alper, Office of the Commercial Counsellor in the Embassy in Tehran, Presentation on Country by Deputy of Commercial Counsellor, presentation on Iran Islamic Republic.

⁴⁴ Preferential Trade Agreement between Government of Turkish Republic and Government of Iran Islamic Republic, dated 29.01.2014 <http://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/default.aspx>

had a repercussion, saying: UAEK is an institution which is already under the monopoly of several countries and its reports are questionable, he said “having the nuclear power by Iran would be beneficial for all Islamic world” and described an important process which he began to act with a strategy to become a regional power.⁴⁵ In this context, a possible US intervention worries the Middle Eastern geography.

Many people including the government officials in Turkey think that Turkey would be subjected to the big financial and emotional damages in this issue. Rıfat Hisarcıklıođlu, the president of TOBB, stated that if US intervened to Iran, then the country, which would be subjected to the big damage, would be Turkey as being in gulf war. Yigit Alpogan, the Secretary of National Security Council, travelled to USA for official visiting by the end of 18th January. Alpogan, who met Condoleezza Rice, the US Secretary of State, declared that he supported USA on Iran issue. In the main agenda of National Security Council meeting, the crisis between Iran and US, and the attitude, which Turkey would have against the possible intervention by US, were discussed. Furthermore, it was also decided to invite the Iranian Government to the reconciliation.⁴⁶

In 2006, Iran carried out the operations against the PKK/Pejak organization in its territory. This attitude of Iran was evaluated by some authors as a political maneuver. Because, Iran desires to obtain the support of Turkey against the problems which Iran experiences with US. According to Sami Kohen, “action of Iran against PKK just while Turkey tries to obtain the support from US on this crisis is a good maneuver that is calculated well, if it is not a coincidence in terms of timing. Hot pursuit by Iranian powers to “Pejak” militants, which are considered as the extension of PKK in order to destroy them within Iraq, and meanwhile, bombing the targets in Qandil Mountain, where PKK also sets up the base, are the actions which will satisfy Ankara, at first sight.

Tehran management carried out this comprehensive operation against the Kurdish activists, without doubt, considering its security. After all, "the existence and activity of Pejak worry Iran. However, there are also other reasons why Tehran countercharges against the militants entering from the Iraqi border by now. The first reason, coming to the mind, is the desire of Iran to pull Turkey by its side in the crisis arising from nuclear program of Iran. In

⁴⁵ŞAHİN, Mehmet, “IrakBağlamında Türk-Amerikan İlişkileri”, M. Aydın & Ç. Erhan (eds.), *Beş Deniz Havzasında Türkiye*, Ankara: Siyasal Kitabevi, 2006.

⁴⁶“Türkiye-İran İlişkileri Stratejik Ortaklıktan Çatışmaya: Füze Kalkanı'ndan PKK ve Karayılan Olayına”, *TÜRKSAM*, 12.10.2011

other words, Iran expects to gain the sympathy and support of Turkish public opinion acting against PKK and its supporters. PKK terrorist organization has been engaged in the terrorist activities against Turkey for many years. According to an allegation published in Cumhuriyet newspaper, USA will also play the PKK card against Iran thereafter, thus implementing the policy which it desires easily on Iran.

The most important agenda item was the natural gas in economy field between two countries until 2006. Turkey wishes to conclude more agreements on natural gas with Iran. However, due to the restrictions by USA, Turkey could not conclude the trade agreements exceeding US\$ 20 billion. For example, it concluded the agreement on natural gas in the amount of US\$ 23 billion with Iran in 1996. Due to the pressure from USA, this agreement was interrupted in 2000. The natural gas flow via Iran was provided in 2002 and Turkey bought 2 billion m³ of natural gas in 2002, 3 billion m³ in 2003, and 4 billion m³ in 2004. However, Turkey demanded the revision of prices due to the reason which the natural gas from Iran was expensive in 2005. When Iran did not make discount in the natural gas price, Turkey applied to the International Arbitration.⁴⁷

The dimension of economic relations between Turkey and Iran has always been important, but the progress at the economic axis of bilateral relations during the recent years attracts the attention. Recep Tayyip Erdogan, the Prime Minister, stated his satisfaction due to increasing of trade volume up to US\$ 7 billion which was US\$ 1.2 billion and targeted as US\$ 5 billion during his meeting Parviz Davudi, the First Assistant of the President of Republic in his visit in Tehran, 2006, and mentioned the new target as US\$ 10 billion. This target was raised to US\$ 20 billion as of 2008. Likewise, Mahmud Ahmedinejad, the President of Republic, interpreted that reaching of trade volume to US\$ 20 billion in 2011 was a target which might be achieved considering the existing potentials during his meeting Mehmet Şimşek, the Minister of State who was in Tehran for meetings of 20th Turkish-Iranian Mixed Economic Commission on November.⁴⁸

A conference was held on “Developing the Turkish-Iranian Trade and Economic Cooperation” based on developing the economic and commercial relations between Turkey and Iran in Tehran on 27th January. Kürşat Tüzmen, the Minister of State, said that this visit was made at the framework of developing the economic and commercial relations of Turkey

⁴⁷ Türkiye-İran ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

⁴⁸ÜZÜMCÜ, Adem; "Türkiye'nin Enerji Güvenliği ve Dış Politika Yansımaları", *Uluslararası IV. Türk Dış Politikası Sempozyum Tebliğleri: Yeni Dönemde Türk Dış Politikası*, Ed. Osman B. Dinçer ve öte., Ankara, USAK (Uluslararası Stratejik Araştırmalar Kurumu), Şubat 2010, ss. 171-202

with its neighboring countries before he fled with Turkish businessmen group consisting of 160 persons to Tehran, and mentioned that the representatives from the sectors of steel-iron, automotive, electric-electronics, plastic-rubber, cosmetics, leather and textile, home appliances, illumination and construction materials and from other sectors from Turkey participated in this visit.

Mesud Mirkazemi, the Iranian Minister of Trade, also attended this conference held in Tehran, and emphasized that the economic relations between two countries developed through the agreements on customs, transportation and taxation. Tüzmen, the Minister of State, also pointed out the developing economic relations between two countries and repeated that the trade volume might reach to US\$ 20 billion, and mentioned that the cooperation in energy and infrastructure investments should also have been developed as well as cooperation in the banking and customs in the bilateral relations. He also said that Turkey was ready for making investment in the amount of US\$ 10 billion in Iran, and US\$ 6 billion out of it would be in the energy sector.⁴⁹

Upon the nuclear program of Iran was perceived by the Western countries as an international problem, the economic relations between Turkey and Iran were not a matter which was concerned by two countries only, but became an issue which was also monitored carefully by USA and European Union. The Western countries expect Turkey to revise the economic relations with Iran based on the economic sanctions which they apply to Iran due its nuclear program. Turkey continues to form its policies in this issue according to the economic requirements.⁵⁰

Reflection of US-Iranian relations to the Turkish-Iranian relations and insisting by Turkey on acting according to its national interests are not a new fact; for example, USA requested the international companies which do business with Libya and Iran to obey the sanctions based on the Iran-Libya Sanctions Act-ILS in 1996, and Turkey objected to this sanction decision and developed the commercial relations with Iran. Turkey insisted on which ILSA did not cover the commercial relations with Iran, and defended that since the natural gas agreement in the amount of US\$ 20 billion, signed by Turkey and Iran on August 1996, was concluded on May 1995 before acknowledgement of ILSA, it could not be evaluated within the sanction decisions. Today, it may be possible to say that Turkey intends to maintain and

⁴⁹ÖZPEK, Burak Bilgehan; "En Uzun On Yıl: 11 Eylül Sonrası Ortadoğu", *Ortadoğu Etütleri*, Cilt 3, No 2, Ocak 2012, ss. 183-215

⁵⁰Türkiye-İran ilişkileri Türk Basını 2000-2006, Şiilik ve Sünnilik, Published MA Dissertation.

develop the economic relations with Iran. Turkey signed a Memorandum of Understanding with Iran in order to enhance the cooperation in energy sector in 2008 when the sanction decisions were şn question due to the nuclear program of Iran.⁵¹

Erdogan, the Prime Minister, who made speech in the European Policy Center in Brussel, the capital city of Belgium, harshly responded to the suggestions on which interruption of relations by Turkey with Iran, and emphasized that the trade volume in the bilateral relations exceeded US\$ 10 billion and Turkey imported 10 billion m³ of natural gas from Iran. Considering that 20% of Turkey's natural gas need is met by Iran and the balance in the commercial relations between Turkey and Iran is in favor of Iran, it is understood well the intention of Turkey to develop economic and commercial relations with Iran. The conference on "Development of Turkish-Iranian Economic and Commercial Relations", which was held in Tehran during the last week, should also be evaluated at this framework.⁵²

The Prime Minister, Recep T. Erdogan, will visit Iran third time as the Prime Minister during 26th-27th October. This visit attracts the attention, since it coincides with a period when both Iran and Turkey are in the international political agenda as of foreign policy that they implement. Iran, which has occupied an important place in the international agenda due to the nuclear program for a long time, has come into the forefront due to the problematic presidency of Republic elections, post-election protests and intensified in-regime discussions and finally, negotiations with 5+1 group, again.

Turkey has become the center of attention due to which it completes the negotiations that Turkey has carried out with Iraq and Syria for a long time with a number of agreements, subsequently organizes the "High Level Strategic Cooperation Meetings" with these two countries and to the tensions which occurred in its relations with Israel. Considering the "special" relation of Iran with Iraq and "alliance" with Syria, the high level visits from Turkey, which already has the good relations with Iran, to Iran attract the attention.

The nuclear issue was also brought into the agenda during visiting of Erdogan on December 2006, and the Iranian party said that they cooperated with UAEA and Iranian nuclear program was under the audit of Agency. By the middle of 2007, Turkey moved away from its passive and abstaining attitude and began to "stand" between Iran and West during

⁵¹ÜZÜMCÜ, Adem; "Türkiye'nin Enerji Güvenliği ve Dış Politika Yansımaları", *Uluslararası IV. Türk Dış Politikası Sempozyum Tebliğleri: Yeni Dönemde Türk Dış Politikası*, Ed. Osman B. Dinçer ve öte., Ankara, USAK (Uluslararası Stratejik Araştırmalar Kurumu), Şubat 2010, ss. 171-202

⁵²Yalçın Sırakaya, *Geçmişten günümüze İran: Tarih, Siyaset, Toplum ve Kültür*.

the negotiations. The negotiations between Iran and EU-3 on nuclear issue that was interrupted restarted with the intervention from Turkish Government on April; Ali Laricani, the Secretary of Iranian National Higher Security Council and the chief negotiator on nuclear issues, and Javier Solana, Higher Representative of EU, met in Ankara.¹⁹ Upon Barack Obama elected as the US President on November 2008, Turkey announced that it might be the peacemaker in the negotiations between Iran and USA, but no such demand was received from the parties. Finally, Turkey wished to host the negotiations which started between Iran and 5+1 group (members of UN Security Council + Germany) on 1st October 2009, but the negotiations started in Geneva.

As the closeness in Turkish-Iranian relations is evaluated, the indicators and facts must be read carefully. When we look at Iran and Turkey via today's reality considering the evaluations related to the history and geography that are used in order that Turkish foreign policy gains the depth, we see two states which are almost equal to each other in Middle East. These two states within the periphery of Arabic world implement the policies with broad perspective in order to avoid any security threatening toward them in Middle East and also to gain the political and economic efficiency in Middle East. Iran and Turkey cooperate in security field within the context of anti-terrorism. When the evaluation is made on security, it is possible that both countries may perceive the threatening from each other.

Iran's policy on exporting the regime caused the security concerns in Turkey. On the other hand, when one looks at from Iran to Turkey, it is possible to determine that there was an instability which has elapsed for twenty five years within the scope of anti-terrorism just beyond the border. As the hotter and more fundamental issue, the Iran's nuclear program is the essential heading in the evaluation of two countries' relations regarding the security. Turkey doesn't question the Iran's right to produce and use the nuclear power, but objects to the production of nuclear weapon. Since such development, which has the potential to greatly shake the balance between two countries, concerns the international agenda as well as the security and defense of Turkey, the brain storm is made on a line from peaceful solutions to the military operations in this issue. Turkey has an attitude on a peaceful solution in the nuclear crisis and defends that diplomatic channels must be maintained open.

Another dimension of Turkish-Iranian relations is the trade and economy. In this field, it is thought that there are significant developments during the recent years. During the last several years, the trade volume between two countries is between US\$ 5 and 10 billion.

Turkey's export to Iran has increased about two folds since 2006. As the goods, which are exported by Turkey to Iran, are notably the machine, iron-steel and motorized land vehicles, the goods that are imported from Iran to Turkey are the mineral fuels and oils. Turkey's total exportation to Iran was US\$ 2 million as of 2009, the importation from Iran was about US\$ 3 million. Turkey's exportation to Iran increased 33% during January-November period of 2010 rather than during the same period of last year and became US\$ 2.7 billion. An importation also increased 55% during the same period and reached to US\$ 7 billion. Furthermore, the commissions from both states have met regularly in the Mixed Economic Council and Common Border Trade Council and have signed the memorandums of understanding on commercial relations since 2007.⁵³

⁵³2003 Memorandum of Understanding on Mixed Economic Commission between the Governments of Turkish Republic and Iran Islamic Republic

CHAPTER 3

1. CHANGING PERCEPTION BETWEEN TURKEY-SAUDI ARABIA AFTER 2002

In order to understand the changing perception in the relations between Saudi Arabia and Turkey after 2002, it would be beneficial to look at the historical process of the past of Turkish-Saudi Arabian relations. Saudi Arabia, which is the biggest and most powerful country of Arabian peninsula, was established by Saud family eight years after the First World War as a result of long fight against the Ottoman Empire. Therefore, there was a negative perception against Turks, especially by the effect of UK that was their alliance during the period after establishing the state. In general, the relations between Turkey and Saudi Arabia were cold historically. There were many conflicts between Saud family and Ottoman State which held the Arabian peninsula during 19th century and at the beginning of 20th century.⁵⁴

Ottoman State punished the Saud family who created frequently the problem several times during 19th century. The “Holy Lands” that had been held by Turks for centuries fell under the domination of Huseyin, the Mecca Sheriff, first, and then, of Saud family and this coldness continued. It was not possible to establish the close relations between Riyadh and Ankara due to the differences between their political regimes and economic and social structures throughout the history of Republic.⁵⁵ In fact, Saudi Kingdom is a state which two families are dominant. Saud family (grandsons of Muhammed bin Saudi) controls the economic and political areas, and Sheikh family (the grandsons of Muhammed bin Abdulvahhab) the social and religious lives. When the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia was proclaimed in 1932, even though Turkey was the first country which recognized it, the relations between two countries were generally at the lower level. Since Saudi Arabia, where about one hundred thousand Turks lived who mostly worked as the construction workers, restaurant operator, barber, car mechanics, furniture dealers, is a kingdom which is based on the Sharia Law, Republic of Turkey that was secular and turned its face to the West was the first country among the countries that Saudi Arabia had stood away from in the region for a long time.⁵⁶

⁵⁴ Muhittin Ataman, *Türkiye-Saudi Arabistan İlişkileri: Temkinli İlişkilerden Çok-Taraflı Birlikteliğe*, Ortadoğu

⁵⁵ Ortadoğu Analiz Eylül’09 Cilt 1 - Sayı 9 Işıl Işık Bostancı, Saudi Arabistan Krallığı’nın Resmen İlan Edilmesinden Önce Arabistan Bölgesi, Fırat Üniversitesi Orta Doğu Araştırmaları Dergisi, Cilt:1, Sayı:2, 2003

⁵⁶ Analiz, 2009, Cilt 1, Sayı 9, s.73-77

Republic of Turkey, which was established upon collapsing of Ottoman State recognized the political independencies of states which were established on its territory. It concluded a Friendship and Peace Agreement with the Kingdom of Hejaz and Nejd that was established by the Saud family immediate after its establishment on 3rd August 1929 and established the diplomatic relations with new state, and announced that Turkey accepted its political independence and integrity of territory. However, there was not any significant positive development in the relations of both countries until 1980s⁵⁷. Two countries, which their political regimes were different from the proclamation of Republic to 1980s, had the important bilateral relations upon Ekmeleddin İhsanoğlu was elected as the Secretary General of Islamic Conference Organization. A short-term improvement occurred in the low-profiled relations during 1960s. King Faisal made a short-term visit to Turkey at the framework of conference that was held in order to develop the idea of Islamic union in 1966, and this visit was the first and single visit in long-term at the King level from Saudi Arabia to Turkey.

When King Faisal did not receive any respond to his visit, the timid attitudes were maintained. After 1983, Turkey experienced the important changes in political and economic areas. It is a fact which is known well that Özal governments, which left their marks on this period, started a restructuring process in the political and economic areas in Turkey.⁵⁸ In this context, the important developments occurred with the Muslim countries, notably with the Middle Eastern countries.

Özal's Turkey adopted a positive approach toward Saudi Arabia in order to be successful in export-based economic development model and to meet the oil need of country securily. The important developments in the bilateral relations also reflected to the mutual visits and in 1984, Kenan Evren, the President of Republic, and in 1985, Turgut Özal, the Prime Minister, visited Saudi Arabia. Abdullah, the Crown Prince of Saudi Arabia also visited Turkey in 1984 and the important developments occurred in the economic dimension. Turkey, which adopted the international expansion strategy, increased the export to that country. Turkish firms started to provide the significant contracting services and Turkish entrepreneurs began to make investments to the different sectors in Saudi Arabia.⁵⁹

⁵⁷Zekeriya Kurşun, *Basra Körfezi'nde Osmanlı-İngiliz. Çekişmesi, Katar'da Osmanlılar 1871-1916*, Türk Tarih Kurumu Yayınları, Ankara, 2004, s29

⁵⁸ Geçmişten Geleceğe Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri, Ortadoğu Analizi, Kasım, cilt10, sayı23.

⁵⁹Muhittin Ataman, *Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri: Temkinli İlişkilerden Çok-Taraflı Birlikteliğe*, Ortadoğu Analiz, 2009, Cilt 1, Sayı 9, s.73-77

It is observed that the important breaking occurred in the relations of two countries during the First Gulf War by the end of Cold War. Turkey, which had a decisive attitude based on the United Nations' decisions and US policy, gained the confidence of Saudi Arabia. Upon ending of Cold War policy, it was observed that it began to occur parallels in the foreign policy of two countries.

Saudi Arabia donated the oil in the amount of US\$ 1.2 billion to Turkey and in the amount of US\$ 1 billion to the Turkish Defense Fund in order to compensate the financial losses of Turkey due to Anti-Saddam policy of Turkey, and Süleyman Demirel, the Prime Minister, visited Saudi Arabis as an indicator of which bilateral relations were developed in 1993. The instabilities in Turkish internal policy during 1990s also caused the instabilities in the foreign policy. The improvements were found at least in the basis of discourse during Erbakan-Çiller coalition that came to power in 1996. Subsequently, the tense weather occurred in the bilateral relations during the process of 28th February. A crisis occurred in the relations of two countries before 2002 general elections which resulted with establishment of the government of Justice and Development Party (AK Party).

The crisis, occurred due to the reactions from Turkey against pulling down of Ajjad Fortress that was built in Mecca during Ottoman period, was eliminated without growing.⁶⁰ Within the context of all of these developments, AK Party came to the power under the negative perception about Turkey in Middle East after 2002 election and began to develop the moving capability in Middle East geography where such negative perceptions were available.

1.1 Relations during AK Party Period After 2002

AK Party government activated a serious restructuring process in the relations with Muslim countries. Relations of AK Party Government and Turkey-Arab countries mostly started as the “confidence building measures” policy. In this context, first of all, it was tried to overcome the problems and then, the works were carried out on development of cooperation areas.

As the deviation was observed in the traditional Western-oriented regional foreign policy of Turkey, adoption of new understanding by the Arab countries took longer. At this framework, it was thought that the relations with Saudi Arabia, which dependency to the West

⁶⁰Geçmişten Geleceğe Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri, Ortadoğu Analizi, Kasım, cilt10, sayı23

continued, but the interests conflicted with the West gradually would be improved through AK Party government. In the event that Turkey would be excluded upon its regional initiatives would increase, Ankara would come closer to Israel and the West and this would be contrary to the interests of Saudi Arabia. As a result of which Saudi Arabia and Turkey were affected by the terrorist actions and they had to implement the policies conflicting with the West, their resoluteness on moving together in maintaining the regional stability made two countries come closer to each other.⁶¹ This process also changed the important perception parameters about the bilateral relations of two countries as well.

After 11th September attacks, fighting against Al-Qaida terrorist organization, which led to the destruction of relations of Saudi Arabia with the West and became the menace to Saudi Government, caused that Saudi officials and Turkish officials had the similar concerns. As Saudi Arabia acknowledged the Turkey's Wester-oriented policy, Turkey abandoned to marginalize Saudi Kingdom. Invasion of Iraq by USA worried both countries, and Saudi Arabian officials showed the similar attitudes in the Iraqi neighboring countries platform which Turkey initiated.⁶²

Many official visits were made at the ministerial level (foreign affairs, foreign trade and finance) between two countries in 2003. Saudi Arabia, which began to lose its confidence gradually against the Western countries, considered Turkey as the alternative investment area under the ruling of AK Party and this led to starting of many economic initiatives between Turkey and Saudi Arabia and to the processes which might cause the changing and developing of existing perception. At this framework, the Convention on Establishing of Turkish-Saudi Business Council was signed in Riyadh on 1st October 2003, and this council started to operate in 2004. It was decided to establish the investment fund under the coordination of Jeddah Chamber of Commerce and Industry and Istanbul Chamber of Commerce (ITO), and to be operated by an international institution on May 2005 in order to encourage the Gulf countries to make investment in Turkey.⁶³

Turkey and Saudi Arabia signed the security cooperation agreement on 12th February 2005 and the Agreement was signed by Abdülkadir Aksu, the Minister of Internal Affairs in name of Turkey and Prince Naif bin Abdülaziz, the Minister of Internal Affairs in name of

⁶¹Muhittin Ataman, *Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri: Temkinli İlişkilerden Çok-Taraflı Birlikteliğe*, Ortadoğu Analiz, 2009, Cilt 1, Sayı 9, s.73-77

⁶²Zekeriya Kurşun, *Basra Körfezi'nde Osmanlı-İngiliz. Çekişmesi, Katar'da Osmanlılar 1871-1916*, Türk Tarih Kurumu Yayınları, Ankara, 2004, s29

⁶³ <http://www.ito.org.tr/wps/portal>

Saudi Arabia. Accordingly, it was decided by two countries to struggle against terrorism at the international level together and to fight against the narcotic. In particular, after Ekmeleddin İhsanoğlu became the Secretary General of Islamic Conference Organization (İKÖ) in Jeddah by early 2005, it was observed intensification in the relations between two countries.⁶⁴

Just 40 years after King Faisal from Saudi Arabia visited Turkey in order to attend an international meeting in Istanbul, 1966, for the first time, another Saudi Arabian king visited Turkey officially in 2006 and 2007. The subsequent visits and the big delegations accompanying the king during visits became the indicators of which the relations between two countries developed positively. King Abdullah visited Ankara with a delegation consisting of 400 persons including the ministers, businessmen, bureaucrats and King family on 8th August 2006. During this historical visit, it was announced that the Turkish and Saudi businessmen agreed upon making common investment between two countries.

The joint declaration was published which two countries agreed upon and was signed by Ali Babacan and Suud Al-Faisal, the Ministers of Foreign Affairs during the visit by Ali Babacan, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of that period on October 2007. In that joint declaration, those points were emphasized. “More intensive cooperation and negotiation in the regional issues, making the high level mutual visits regular, increasing the cooperation in struggle with terror and crime, encouraging the firms to make more investment mutually, removing all blocks which are encountered with in this field and cooperation in banking.” As a requirement of agreement in the joint declaration, Saudi party would encourage the private sector to make investment in Turkey, the existing and possible opportunities would be introduced to the businessmen from two countries, the transportation possibilities would be enhanced, the transit passages would be facilitated and the cooperation would be made in energy.⁶⁵

It would be possible to disclose or publish the material related to the defense industry or information which would be exchanged mutually to the third parties with the writing consent from the original owner of them only. Parties would observe the copyrights and other restrictions related to the reproduction, copying, using or distribution of all materials, products and information that would be provided by either party at the framework of this Agreement.

⁶⁴<http://cidde.bk.mfa.gov.tr/ShowInfoNotes.aspx?ID=121158>

⁶⁵Muhittin Ataman, *Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri: Temkinli İlişkilerden Çok-Taraflı Birlikteliğe*, Ortadoğu Analiz, 2009, Cilt 1, Sayı 9, s.73-77

Protection of confidential information, document and material: Either party would guarantee to handle the confidential materials, project drafts, technical specifications and other confidential information to be exchanged pursuant to this agreement in accordance with the national law and regulations. Parties would keep all these materials and information confidential as much as the protection which they provide to their own confidential materials and information.⁶⁶ All these explained matters may be considered as the most important matters regarding the Agreement. In this context, many subheadings such as Passport and immigration procedures, settlement of disputes took place within the scope of this agreement, and in the historical sense, it may be evaluated as the comprehensive agreement on mutual relations and agreements between Turkey and Saudi Arabia.

Ali Babacan attended the meeting held by Islamic Conference Organization in Jeddah by the early days of 2009. At the same time, the Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan also visited Riyadh one-day. Between 3–6 February 2009, the President of Republic Abdullah Gül went to Saudi Arabia with a big delegation in order to pay a return visit to King Abdullah and to discuss the bilateral relations and regional and international issues which interested closely two countries. Gül demanded from Saudis to prefer Turkey in economic investment, education, tourism and health areas during his visit. Gül, who was welcomed by King Abdullah at the airport, made a speech in the Council Assembly during his visit.⁶⁷

Turkey signed the “Framework Convention on Economic Cooperation” with the countries of Gulf Cooperation Council. With this convention, the free trade zone would be established between Turkey, Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, United Arab Emirates, Qatar and Saudi Arabia, and the convenience would be provided in the visa procedures of citizens from aforesaid countries.⁶⁸ In this context, it is understood that in fact, Turkey approaches to Arabian peninsula as a whole, not to the countries one by one. It is expected that this visit, which is the milestone regarding the development of political and economic relations between two countries, would also lead to increasing of interest by other Arabian countries in Turkey. One of the most important issues was the security during the visit by King Abdullah. As Saudi Arabia was the custom alliance of USA, it initiated to break down the dependency to USA after 11th September events and in this context, Saudi government, which began to worry about American/Israeli-centered regional arrangements, developed the close relations with

⁶⁶ “Agreement on Training, Technical and Scientific Cooperation in Military Area” between the Governments of Turkish Republic and Saudi Arabia Kingdom, dated 24 May 2010” <http://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/default.aspx>

⁶⁷ Abdullah Aydoğan Kalabalık, Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan Yakınlaşması ve Mısır'ın Tutumu, SETA

⁶⁸ Geçmişten Geleceğe Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri, Ortadoğu Analizi, Kasım, cilt10, sayı23

Turkey which had the similar worries and was one of the most efficient and important countries in the region. Experiencing such sharp changing processes in perception toward Turkey also caused the exchange of ideas on the regional issues such as Lebanon, Palestine and Iraq.⁶⁹

We should express that there are some fundamental dialogs which Saudi Arabia and Turkey share; Palestine, terrorism and regional stability. Both countries support Palestine before United Nations (UN) on Palestine issue. In fact, these dialogs, which we speak about, are the desire to provide reference to the stability and security in Middle East and Arabian peninsula. Turkey and Saudi Arabia wish to move comfortably in close vicinity and to establish the close relations with the countries in this region. Resoluteness of Saudi Arabistan and Turkey on moving together in order to protect the regional stability and being affected by terrorist actions made two countries come closer.⁷⁰

The regional issues have the priority regarding the external threats toward Saudi Arabia, as we stated above. We may list the external threats as future instability of Iraq which started with invasion of Iraq by USA in 2003, instability initiatives by the supra-state actors such as Hizbullah and Hamas, interventionism of USA as being in Lebanon and Palestine, and radical block forming and its derivatives. In such case, it may not be thought that the relations between two countries are limited with economy. In this context, an important bilateral agreement was signed between Republic of Turkey and Saudi Arabia Kingdom considering the friendship between two countries and believing that this cooperation would be the benefit of both countries upon wishing to develop the cooperation in security and struggle with drug and psychotropic substances in a widest extent.⁷¹

One of the most important external issues regarding Saudi Arabia today is the Shiah riot in Yemen and its impact on Saudi regime. Hot conflicts that started upon Houthis powers announced that they made a Saudi fighter jet crash and invaded the Saudi territory on 3rd November 2009, ended up with failure of Saudi powers. Subsequently, Saudi Arabia could recover the lands with diplomatic initiatives. At this framework, it is observed that Turkey

⁶⁹Muhittin Ataman, *Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri: Temkinli İlişkilerden Çok-Taraflı Birlikteliğe*, Ortadoğu Analiz, 2009, Cilt 1, Sayı 9, s.73-77

⁷⁰ <http://www.21yyte.org/tr/arastirma/suriye/2012/08/09/6705/suriyede-kurt-yayilma-etkisinin-sonucu-turkiyede-teror-ve-siddet>

also considers the security concerns of Saudi Arabia about Yemen. When one looks at the statements made by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, it is observed that Turkey implements a foreign policy which Turkey supports the stability in Yemen and its territorial integrity. Furthermore, in the statement made by the Prime Minister Erdogan related to the policies of Saudi Arabian King, he shows that Turkey supports the regional policies of Riyadh.⁷²

Even though there are common policies between Turkey and Saudi Arabia on Iran and widespreading of nuclear weapons, it is observed that there are some differences in wording. Saudi regime fears that Iran's policy on gaining the nuclear power would lead to destroy the power balances in favor of Iran in the region and in this case, the Persian Gulf would go under a serious threat. The primary policy of Saudi Arabia is to disarm the region from nuclear weapons and to prevent such initiatives. Hence, it attracts the attention that Saudi government purchased the weapon in the amount of about US\$ 60 billion only from USA by the effect of increasing security threat in 2010. In relation with Iran issue, as the instabilities experienced in the sides of Iraq and Yemen push Riyadh to establish close cooperation with the countries in the region where Turkey is also included, on one hand, and both to increase its military capacity and to establish the military cooperation with USA upon directing it to purchase the weapon directly, on the other hand.⁷³

Despite the fact that both countries clearly expressed that they did not want the widespreading of nuclear weapons in the region, it was observed that Turkey implemented a foreign policy on establishing the cooperation with Iran through the dialog process. Except the nuclear issue, Turkey considers Iran as an actor that Turkey may establish the cooperation with in the solution of problems as a country in the region. It is feared that exclusion of Iran may make difficult the solution of problems. Despite of it, it is observed that both countries implement more sensitive foreign policy on Iran and Turkey understands the worries of Saudi Arabia about Iran. As being understood, changing Turkish perception in Middle East starts to show its effect on all states.⁷⁴

Saudi Arabian-Turkish relations, which gained a significant acceleration in the economic, political and military senses during the last decade, tend to raise toward strategic

⁷²Şahin KESKİN, Türkiye Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri Ankara Riyad-Dostluk Hattı.

⁷³ 19.01.2010, *Suudi Arabistan Türk Konseyi Resmi İnternet Sitesi*, <http://www.saturkkonseyi.net/ReadNews.aspx?ID=56> (a.d. 03.11.2010)

cooperation at the regional level with Arab Spring. Arab revolutions provided the basis where Turkey and Saudi Arabia, two stable and important actors of the region, might establish more cooperation. The factor, which causes the relations between two countries moving toward multi-dimensional cooperation at this level, is the instability and distrust atmosphere that Arab Spring causes in Middle East. Within this conjuncture, the alliance relations were destroyed and the regional balances entered into the restructuring period. In such environment, Turkey was considered by Saudi Arabia as the strategic partner with its military, economic, population and historical-cultural characteristics: Supporting of Saudi Arabian thesis by Turkey on Syria issue strengthened the Ankara-Riyadh relation.

It deems that it would be in favor of Saudi Arabia's interests that Turkey provided a stable structure in the region. In this scope, it was observed that an active foreign policy was implemented on providing a stable structure in Iraq so as not creating the problem for entire region. Use of initiative by Turkey in Palestine issue, crises in Lebanon and finally, solution of Yemen issue through diplomatic ways is considered both by Arabic regimes and Riyadh in private very important. As a result, it should be stated that the relations between two countries would continue by developing.⁷⁵ In this context, AK Party government correctly followed the new conjuncture developing in Middle East during 2002-2014, and oriented the direction of political system which stuck with the internal political applications toward Middle East. The turning became a fully active foreign policy line and Turkey came out of its shell as a country which stood away from the regional problems for a long time and in the regional sense, the close relations were established and it was tried to provide the sustainability on this subject. The instruments, used for sustainability, were the bilateral agreements which were deemed important in the international systems. Consequently, another breaking point regarding the relations of Saudi Arabia and Turkey will occur with Arab Spring process.

⁷⁵ Veysel Ayhan, Geçmişten Geleceğe Türkiye-Suudi Arabistan İlişkileri, Ortadoğu Analizi, 2010, Cilt 2, sayı 23.

CHAPTER 4

1. CHANGING PERCEPTION BETWEEN TURKEY-EGYPT AFTER 2002

It is difficult to understand Middle East, because the history of understanding Middle East is the history of reestablish the political and social topography of region in consistent with the political interventions rather than pure scientific curiosity. Creating an approach, excluding those residues left by history, requires a theoretical preparation. Even though the steps, which are taken without making such preparation, are formed by the naïve or apolitical motivations, they raise on an intellectual platform that the Orientalism determines. Even, the name “Middle East” is the manifestation of this political curiosity. For these reasons, understanding Middle East, interpreting any political dynamic within the region, and even trying to study the physical characteristics may serve to various political investments. The Orientalist discourses establish the Middle Eastern fact through the Cultural or Developmental theories which they are added, and operate this construction as a social scientific power inverter.⁷⁶

Ottomon Empire didn't have the social classes and economic systems which required the colonist policy formed by an interesting coalition of early capitalist development and state-private sector initiation. Since the Ottomans were the sultans of a geography where economically depended on the West, even though they knew the nature of reforms which should have been made and despite of existence of the bureaucrats such as Mithat Pasha whom even the Westerners took example, they could not prevent the disintegration.⁷⁷

The reform processes and wars of Ottoman Empire during the last period brought the big financial burdens with them. Ottomans that lived in a debt regime financially beyond the broder borrowed their first debt by the middle of 19th century and since they could not put that debt to good use in investment more profitable than the debt, they experienced the first

⁷⁶ ÇALIŞKAN, Koray, Ortadoğu siyaseti ve toplumlarını anlama yolları, İ.Ü. Siyasal Bilgiler Fakültesi Dergisi <http://www.arastirmax.com/system/files/dergiler/274/makaleler/39/arastirmax-ortadoğu-siyaseti-toplumlarini-anlama-yollari.pdf>

⁷⁷ Değişen Mısır ve Yeni Dönemde Türkiye- Mısır İlişkileri, Ortadoğu STRATEJİK Araştırma Merkezi

financial crisis during the last quarter of the same century. Immediate after those crises which were resulted with handling of debt management by the Westerners, they lost the financial control and the country disintegrated soon afterwards. After collapsing, the bureaucratic elit, which established the republic in Anatolian geography, aimed to establish a nation-state which was economically independent in this humble geography and the unique democracy (which works, even if it is difficult) of Middle East began to emerge. Other parts of Ottoman's Middle East would have to tackle with new sovereigns of the region for a long time and the heritage of this period would determine their socio-political chemistry.⁷⁸

Abdel Nasser, who was elected as the President of Republic soon after the proclamation of Republic (in 1956), promised Egypt to an independent position and gaining the respect. During this period, Egypt came close to the Socialist Block. An economy policy, which might be deemed as socialist, was implemented with the support from Soviet Union. Egypt led the establishment of Non-Aligned Movement, and nationalized Suez Canal. The agreement on Unite of Syria and Egypt also corresponds to that period. The serious tensions occurred in the relations with Turkey during that period. As Turkey, which worked to establish Baghdad Pact, pressed Syria to sign Baghdad Pact, Egypt tried to prevent the realization of Pact which was contrary to its policies.

It was discussed how the developments in Turkey reflected to Egypt and at which degree these events had impact on internal and external developments of Egypt. In this paper, the primary reason of why Egypt is selected is the central position of this country in Arab world and its intellectual effect and great population. This paper shows that Turkey is considered by Egypt as a model especially during the recent periods and Cairo deems Turkey as an important inspiration source in the problems which Cairo encounters with. For this reason, it is deemed that Turkey is perceived as a model politically and socially in this country.⁷⁹

Failing to improve the economic conditions of country, in contrary, getting worst of Mubarak government gradually during the recent periods were one of the reasons which people went to Tahrir Square by early 2011. However, Mubarak could manage Egypt without encountering many internal problems for 30 years until 2011. Even though it was not possible

⁷⁸ ÇALIŞKAN, Koray, Ortadoğu siyaseti ve toplumlarını anlama yolları, İ.Ü. Siyasal Bilgiler Fakültesi Dergisi <http://www.arastirmax.com/system/files/dergiler/274/makaleler/39/arastirmax-ortadogu-siyaseti-toplumlarini-anlama-yollari.pdf>

⁷⁹ FERHAVİ, Fuat, Türkiye Mısır İkili İlişkilerden Bölgeselliğe USAK, Analist Dergisi, Ortadoğu

to say that there was a real rapprochement between Turkey and Egypt during Mubarak period, the relations steered relatively without problem. The free trade agreement was signed which increased the trade volume at certain degree between two countries on December 2005. There were many official visits at the level of president of republic, prime minister and ministers from 2004.⁸⁰

Turkey's biggest economic partner in Africa is Egypt. Even though this is a positive matter regarding the bilateral relations, when we look at the total trade volume of Turkey, the rate of trade with Egypt is quite low. This shows that the commercial relations have a serious development potential in the future, even if the rate is lower today. There is a free trade agreement between Turkey and Egypt.⁸¹ This agreement is an opportunity regarding development of economic relations. Considering the future plans and potentials of two countries, increasing in the economic relations between Turkey and Egypt would provide the big opportunities to both countries; so, the economic relations must increase significantly. This increase should not be limited with the commercial relations only. Development of relations at the academic, touristic, cultural levels and with NGOs will also allow the development of common economic relations. If the economic partnership is strengthened based on these factors, then both countries will benefit from this significantly.⁸² The bilateral agreements, concluded in this context, will create an important efficiency and perception process in the approaches of two communities to each other.

“Turkish-Egyptian Protocol of Sixth Period Tourism Mixed Commission”, which was signed between Turkey and Egypt within the scope of bilateral relations in Cairo on 6th September 2005, has a significant place. According to this protocol, the agreement was signed between two governments within the scope of Introduction of Tourism, Tourism Education, Tourism Investment. It is deemed that since this protocol, which is an important agreement and must be handled within the scope of bilateral relations of Turkey-Egypt, is within the Tourism field, it will function as a bridge between two communities and will cause the significant change in the perception of communities toward each other, and it was observed that this protocol enhanced the moving capability regarding the relation of Turkey with Egypt

⁸⁰UYSAL, Ahmet, Orta Doğuda Türkiye Algısı: Mısır Algısı, 2011.

⁸¹Türkiye Cumhuriyeti Hükümeti ile Mısır Arap Cumhuriyeti Hükümeti Arasında Serbest Ticaret Anlaşması <http://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/default.aspx>

⁸²ACAR, Mustafa <http://www.sde.org.tr/tr/newsdetail/turkiye-misir-ikili-iliskiler-ve-demokrasi-tecrubeleri-calistayi/3369>

during the course of time. It seems that this tourism Protocol proves the discourse that it is the significant process of development and change between two countries.

Despite of all economic achievements of Turkey, the most serious problem occurs in the export-import balance. Turkey still purchases more imported goods than exported goods. This indicates that Turkish economy is not as strong as it seems. In addition to it, one of the most important economic problems of Turkey is the income distribution today. Even if national income per capita increases in Turkey, there is a great income inequality. This causes the trouble in the community. Egyptian economy has a very significant potential for the future. Even though it has experienced very significant problems in the economy due to the corruptions during the last 40 years, they may be overcome, and it may be looked at the forthcoming process more positively.⁸³ However, if we look at the bilateral relations again, there are not big opportunities regarding the economic partnership between two countries due to the negative situations in the export-import balance of both Turkey and Egypt.⁸⁴

Academic and cultural relations are the relations which also have both political and economic impacts. Therefore, cultural interaction and establishing the academic partnerships are extremely important regarding the development of relations between two countries. Cultural relations between two countries during the modern period starts with Mehmed Akif. Mehmed Akif, who was one of the prominent poets of Turkish society, spent the last period of his life in Cairo. He carried out the important cultural activities such as giving education on Turkish in Egypt and established the important bridges in this field. Establishing the Egyptian Culture Center in Turkey, 2009 and then, establishing Yunus Emre Institute in Egypt are very important regarding the cultural relations. Both language education is provided and different cultural activities are carried out in these culture centers. Besides, the academicians travelled between two countries recently, and furthermore, it was observed that the number of Master Degree and PhD students enhanced mutually.⁸⁵ These examples are the most concrete examples of perception parameters regarding the communities of two countries.

One of the most important cultural relations is the translation services. The translation activities from Arabic to Turkish were in general about religious works until 60s and were the individual works. After 60s, there were important translations in the different fields (politics,

⁸³AKGÜN, Mensur ve GÜNDOĞAR, Sabiha Şenyücel Mısır Türkiye İlişkilerinde Daha İyi Bir Geleceğe Doğru <http://www.tesev.org.tr/assets/publications/file/13032014115738.pdf>

⁸⁴AbdelKhalekFarouk <http://www.sde.org.tr/tr/newsdetail/turkiye-misir-ikili-iliskiler-ve-demokrasi-tecrubeleri-calistayi/3369>

⁸⁵Ortadoğu Analiz, Cilt 4, Sayı, 2, 2010.

thought, al-Benna books, Kutub books), notably in the religious books. During the last decade, the translation works increased more. The translation works are not at the desired level yet, but one should consider that it develops.

As there are such activities on Arabic translation in Turkey, the translations activities in Turkish also increase in Egypt. Recently, a project was initiated to translate many literary works in Turkish to the different languages, and at this framework, the translations to Arabic language are also made. In addition to it, there are 13 Turkish Language departments in Egypt. During the past years, very less student preferred this department. However, it is preferred by many students recently. It is not taught Turkish language only but also Ottoman language and Turkish literature and culture in this department. Development of political relations occurs concurrently with the development of cultural relations. It is expected that the cultural relations develop much more in the forthcoming period. It is thought that the translation activities between two languages will also increase gradually as a result of changing perception between two states.⁸⁶

The commercial relations between Turkey and Egypt are significantly improved recently. During the recent years, investments of Turkey in Egypt have increased gradually and especially, Turkish businessmen have been effective in the Egyptian market during the period of Ak Party governments. In parallel to this, as many foreign investors left from Egypt during the revolution process, Turkish investors increased their investments in Egypt and there is an important perceptive process that they still increase. One may say that the investments of Turkish businessmen in Egypt and the commercial relations may develop more. In this context, the partnerships on infrastructure works are the important supporters. The protocols were signed between Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality and Cairo and Giza municipalities on exchanging the experience; by this way, it is aimed to transfer the experience on Egypt's infrastructure arrangement from Turkey.⁸⁷

When one looks at the Egyptian events from Turkish history perspective, the army has played a very bad role in the Turkish political life for years. Despite of the public support which it was nourished, the army became a bad factor which contributed to the worsen of country conditions at the unique level especially during the coups in 1960, 1971, 1980 and 1997. The history recurs in Egypt in the eyes of Turks. As being for Morsi, Turkish army

⁸⁶SAMY, Ahmed, <http://www.sde.org.tr/tr/newsdetail/turkiye-misir-ikili-iliskiler-ve-demokrasi-tecrubeleri-calistayi/3369>

⁸⁷<https://www.ispark.com.tr/baskan-topbas-kahiredeki-temaslarina-basladi/>

overthrew and judged Adnan Menderes who was the first elected prime minister in the Republic of Turkey, and executed him with his two minister friends in 1960.

It is clear that there is not any Turkish intention to increase the diplomatic tension with Egyptian officials recently. The evidence of it is the returning of ambassador to his office. This means that the reason of why the relations breakdown, in fact, is related to the Egyptian officials who prefer to fight for now. Egypt makes itself being subjected to the results of such step in the political and economic fields. Without doubt, this attitude will have also the repercussions on Turkey.⁸⁸

First of all, without doubt, even though the Turkish acting ambassador would be in Egypt, Turkey lost an important source with this step in order to monitor the flows of events within the country. Furthermore, breakingdown of diplomatic relations means that: the relations would be brought to the past, and would require the changing of occurring conditions. This is a case which is uncertain especially under the tension between two countries for a while now. Secondly, Turkish estimations say that: This would not be effective in long-term considering the depth of relations between two communities. If the same policies are implemented with the data already available in Egypt, then they will not allow the officials to be in office for a long time. Turkish president of republic stated this tendency and likewise, two consultants also pointed out the wish that the relations between two countries would back to the previous depth as being between the Turkish and Egyptian communities differentiating the Egyptian officials and Egyptian people.⁸⁹ Because, the perception of Egyptian people, which changed with AK Party government after 2002, should not be risked during this process.

At today's point, if Turkey really believes the brotherhood of two nations in addition to its interests which are critical for Middle East, Africa and Turkey in Mediterranean, then it must revise the relations with Egypt and must renew them before becoming more necrotized. In this way, Turkey may maintain the projects which it started during the time of Mohamed Morsi, the old president of republic, may support the credit which it granted, may complete the works on free zone that it started and may protect the Turkish businessmen who established the work trusting Turkis state in Egypt from the damages. Even if Egypt appears so negative, it is the intellectual brain of other Arab world. Any country, which loses its

⁸⁸AbdelKhalekFarouk <http://www.sde.org.tr/tr/newsdetail/turkiye-misir-ikili-iliskiler-ve-demokrasi-tecrubeleri-calistayi/3369>

⁸⁹KÜLEBİ ALİ, Stratejik Göstergeler ve Değerlendirmeler, Enerji, Savunma ve Ortadoğu Konularında Sorunlar ve Gelişmele, Tarihiçi Kitabevi.

positive image there, also encounters with the same results in other Arab World. Despite the fact that it is late, if Turkey desires to maintain the activities which it started with Yunus Emre Culture Center and education on Turkish and Turkology that are already available about in 15 universities or departments with the steps which it took recently, then it should revise the relations with Egypt. Turkey has always benefited from intimacy of two nations; if it believes in this intimacy and even, would like to help Ikhwan which was subjected to a big disaster, then the relations with Arabic Republic of Egypt must be reestablished.

It is not acceptable to maintain the Turkish-Egyptian relations via media or through some political messages. His Excellency the President of Republic must assume an initiative immediately. He must have the relations with Egypt being restarted – even if compulsory – recognizing the actual situation today upon considering his invitation on providing the peace saying “the Brother Egyptian society should call the elections as soon as possible” immediate after the coup, because the relations to be established would be the relations between two permanent states. There is not any political importance how Abdel Fattah el-Sisi came to power in the eyes of Egyptians and even of the World as of today. It should be avoided damaging to the relations of two states which need each other via his manner to come to the power. The interests of Turkish and Egyptian people require it. Likewise, this application is also dominant in other practices of Turkey. Which is the leader, whom his hand was shaken during the summit of Turkic Republics in Turkey recently, less dictator or at which degree is it considered the identity of Putin in Turkish-Russian relations that Turkey cares very much? Instead of global dominations on Egyptian people, Turkish-Egyptian relations and history, the essential way in order to serve to our desire to become a regional power, which is important for the future, is to take this medicine, even if it is bitter.⁹⁰

Since Egypt and Turkey preferred the East and West camps, respectively during the Cold War, the relations between two countries were negative. However, this comprehension began to change during 1980s and Egypt had an important place in the expansion of AK Party toward Middle East. New Turkish government considers Egypt as a partner due to its weight in Middle East and as a door to expand toward Africa. Since Egypt economically and politically worsened recently and implemented the policies in parallel to the US and Israeli policies as well as decreasing of its impact on regional problems, Egypt’s leadership position

⁹⁰Ali Hüseyin Bakır, Askeri darbe sonrası Türk-Mısır ilişkilerinin geleceği, <http://www.aljazeera.com.tr/gorus/askeri-darbe-sonrasi-turk-misir-iliskilerinin-gelecegi> Accession date 8.06.2014

was shaken in Arab world.⁹¹ Rising of Turkey in Middle East and returning to the region caused the emergence of idea which Turkey established the Sunni camp under the leadership of Egypt and Saudi Arabia and in particular, new Middle Eastern policy of AK Party government led to a process of establishing “Shiah” camp under the leadership of Iran, Syria and Hezbollah. Turkey entered to the environment that was formed between two camps on devotion and conflict regarding the relations with the West as an impartial and balanced model. In this environment, the relations of Turkey with Egypt were formed between the cooperation and competition in the basis of ruling.⁹²

Upon AK Party came to the power, it was noticed immediately that the group from the past with Islamic tendency in Turkey maintained its achievement in many elections and referandums by softening and democratizing its expressions. This achievement generalized the perception on which Islam and democracy, secularism and democracy and even Islam and secularism could be balanced in the Arab world. Rising of Turkey is carefully followed by the opposition parties and movements, notably by the Muslim Brotherhood as the source of inspiration in Egypt, having the significant social and economic problems. On the other hand, the opposition movements bring forward the Turkish experiences and Turkish model regarding the politics, economy and society in the discussions almost on every subjects. There are many persons who think that at least, it may be used the Turkey’s successful experiences in many areas as well as those who say that Egypt should follo the Turkish model.⁹³

As Turkish experience keeps the youngsters’ complaints on the agenda due to the oppressive ruling and bad economic performance during the recent years, it is a factor which increases the hopes on which the better is possible and demands on change. This model is showed as an example on which a Muslim society may both adopt the democracy and provide the economic development. Even though the change in Turkey occurred in a democratic process, since the democratic process was not possible in Tunisia and Egypt, this change was made with a public movement which was without blood, but damaged to the image of both countries in the international society. It is predicted that the movements, which made the revolution in Egypt and Tunisia, would benefit from the Turkish experiences regarding the

⁹¹Ortadoğu Analiz, Cilt 4, Sayı, 2, 2010.

⁹²<http://www.aljazeera.com.tr/gorus/akp-iktidarinda-dis-politika-altin-devir-ve-arap-يسانلari-sonrasi>

democracy, economic development and foreign policy thereafter. One may say that it would be continued to see Turkey which became the source of inspiration for the aforesaid reforms in the Arabic countries where democratic change was demanded as a model country which would be followed in the economy, healthcare, social services and even foreign policy areas for implementation of a successful democratic system in the countries where the revolution was made during the forthcoming years.⁹⁴ In this context, Egypt-Turkey relations maintained from 2002 when AK Party came to the power to the revolution process with the agreements and developments. However, post-revolution process affected this situation and a conflict atmosphere occurred. In general, when the bilateral agreements are left on the one side of process, and when the perceptive process is evaluated regarding Egypt-Turkey relations both within the state and in the society during post-2002 period, we face with the results of research and polls. In this sense, the perceptive change, occurred between the societies and states in the bilateral relations, would be expressed in the most concrete manner.

As it is expressed that Mubarak regime made Egypt the “sick person of Middle East”, it is mentioned the admiration on the developments which Turkey made during the last decade. Kefaya Movement stated that Turkish experience offered very positive examples to the region far from the radicalism and fanaticism.⁹⁵ As Turkish experience keeps the youngsters’ complaints on the agenda due to the oppressive ruling and bad economic performance during the recent years, it is a factor which increases the hopes on which the better is possible and demands on change. It is emphasized that a Muslim society may both achieve the democratic and economic development. Even though the change in Turkey occurred in a democratic process, since the democratic process was not possible in Tunisia and Egypt, this change was made with a revolution. It is predicted that the movements, which made the revolution in Egypt and Tunisia, would take Turkey as a model regarding the democracy, economic development and foreign policy thereafter.⁹⁶

Since this research aims to show what the Turkish image is in Egypt, it discusses generally the Egyptian society. Research aims to study how Turkey is perceived in four areas. 1) Official view about Turkey as stated in the course books of Egyptian secondary schools; 2) Turkish image in Egyptian media as shown the issues related to Turkey in the major media

⁹⁴Ortadođu Analiz, Cilt 4, Sayı, 2, 2010.

⁹⁵AKTAY, Yasin <http://www.sde.org.tr/tr/newsdetail/turkiye-misir-ikili-iliskiler-ve-demokrasi-tecrubeleri-calistayi/3369>

⁹⁶<http://dergipark.ulakbim.gov.tr>

organs; 3) Turkish image in the Egyptian society and especially in the Egyptian youngsters, and 4) Perception manner of Turkish foreign policy and foreign relations.

Getting closer of Egypt to USA and West changed the view of Egypt on Turkey both in the historical and official opinions. The change in official view is showed as much as possible. Today's views on Turkey are also studied as an important issue in order to show the foreign policy dynamics. Since the reflection of Turkey by the media organs would reflect the official, intellectual and journalists' views, it should also be studied. Media organs are important both as news and information resources regarding the reflection of Turkey and handling the events in the certain aspects. Furthermore, they would provide the clues related to the views of media organs' owners and different ideologic, political and professional groups that are connected with them about Turkey, the media organs are also studied.

As the media subject is limited with the reflection of important events occurred during the last decade to the media, the intellectual view about Turkey and Turks are studied from the secondary resources in the cultural works such as novel, story, poem, movie and serials as well as in the official views. Appearance of a point of view in the official channels or civil media organs doesn't mean that it is directly adopted by the public. So, the views of different rank and files about Turkey are also studied. As the public views are studied, the views of university youth as well as of the intellectuals and leaders are also studied. In studying the media, the pro-government, independent newspapers and the newspapers of different political parties are the important resources. Again, it is also observed that the attitudes of academic personalities and of the religious, political and social groups in the different media organs are also studied.⁹⁷

The relations between Turkey and Egypt, which were the primary countries of Middle East, were subjected to the best and worst periods of history subsequently during the recent years. As the Revolution on 25th January 2011 initiated the process which the relations raised to the top level, the relations fell down to the lowest level upon overthrow of Mohamed Morsi, the elected President of Republic by the military coup on 3rd July 2013. However, the relative dynamism in the Turkey-Egypt relations recently led to the questions in public related to development of a new relation type on Ankara-Cairo line. The news came up that the bilateral meeting would be held between the foreign ministers of Turkey and Egypt during the meetings by the participation of leaders at the framework of 69th General Assembly of United

⁹⁷UYSAL, Ahmet, Orta Doğuda Türkiye Algısı: Mısır Algısı, 2011.

Nations on 24-30 September 2014. This news, which excited some, was interpreted by some as “Where did that come from?” According to the information from different sources, the meeting to be held within the context of UN meetings was determined during the meetings on determining the joint strategy toward Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) in Jeddah and Paris. Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu, the Turkish Minister of Foreign Affairs and Samih Sukri, the Egyptian Minister of Foreign Minister, who met with the occasion of these meetings, agreed upon holding the bilateral meetings in New York and decided that their representatives in UN would organize it. However, the plan could not be implemented. Recep Tayyip Erdogan, the President of Republic, harshly criticized both the coup government under the leadership of Abdel Fattah el-Sisi in Egypt and UN as the institution which legalized the coup in his speech made in the General Assembly of UN on. After the critics of Erdogan, the Egyptian party announced that it cancelled the planned meeting. As Turkey deemed that this cancellation was made due to which Egypt had “complex”, Egypt emphasized that the demand on meeting was made by Turkey implying that it gained a diplomatic move. Even though the meeting is not held, this endeavour indicates that there is a significant softening in the views of Turkey and Egypt toward each other. One may say that it is recognized gradually that maintaining the tension between two states that began in 2013 would not be meaningful anymore.⁹⁸

⁹⁸UYSAL, Ahmet, Orta Doğuda Türkiye Algısı: Mısır Algısı, 2011.

CONCLUSION

Turkish foreign policy attracts the more attention recently. The days, when Turkey chose to stay away from the neighboring region, are left in the past; today, Turkey implements a foreign policy which prefers cooperation rather than face-off and isolation. The close dialog of the country with Middle East led to a battle royal in the region and therefore, this paper discusses the reactions of region about this issue. Of course, the foreign policy is at least a bidirectional process.

Even though it is not thought that a survey, done by Kadir Has University, reflect the truth, it classifies the role of Turkey that must play in Middle Eastern geography. According to the survey, the rate, which Turkey was successful in the policy that was implemented against the developments in Middle East, was found lower than past years. As 65.5 percent of those, who participated in the survey, stated that the events in Syria was the primary issue of Turkish foreign policy, almost half of them found that the Turkish policies toward Syria and Egypt were failed. The rate of those, who find that the Turkish policy against the events in Syria is failed, is 49%. Again, 48% of those, who participated in the survey, found that the policy of Turkey implemented after military coup in Egypt was failed. As 5.2 percent of those, who participat in the survey, defend that Turkey should support the armed opposition powers in Syria, 43.5% of them support the idea that there should not be any international intervention to Syria under any circumstances. The public in Turkey don't want Turkey to be the intervenor of problems between other countries such as Arab-Israel, Iran–USA. In the survey, it is stated the institution which should be efficient in the implementation/execution of Turkish foreign policy as the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. In addition to it, it is deemed that the key of strong foreign policy is increasing the political and military cooperation with other countries.⁹⁹

In other different study, the view of Arab world about Turkey was examined in general through the paper of Meliha Benli Altunışık, Arabic View on Turkey in 2010. As a result, this paper states there are four important developments which affect generally the view of Arabs about Turkey: (a) Coming of Islamic-rooted Ak Party to the power after 2002 elections, (b) Not allowing US Army to invade Iraq with the resolution on 1st March 2003, (c) Officially starting the EU Accession Period in 2005, and (d) Davos Event. The study of

⁹⁹<http://www.khas.edu.tr/news/950>

Altunışık was executed through survey throughout Arabic countries and offered a general approach.

Ak Party government, which won the election with great support from the public from 2002 Elections until 2015, breached the loneliness and peace in Middle East. As being understood from our paper, it signed the bilateral agreements on many subjects with the important countries such as Egypt, Iran and Saudi Arabia that had the significant impact on the region and took out its head from the sand in the Middle Eastern geography. AK Party government tried to show the potential power and efficiency of the Republic of Turkey which moved away from the discourse on loneliness and had maintained its existence for thousand of years to the whole world, notably to the region. It created many pragmatic concepts such as zero problem policy, new Turkish Vision, and Turkey became an important actor in the region. It signed the important bilateral agreements on security, economy, education, culture, technology, industry areas with Iran, Egypt and Saudi Arabia that had the efficient position in the region and as a result of these agreements, the thick walls between the communities were pulled down, and this active foreign policy approach allowed for transforming of negative perception about Turkey for years to a positive process. Agreements on education and culture with Iran, projects on sharing the national archives, agreements on Defense industry with Saudi Arabia, and high level agreement on tourism with Egypt increased the effect coefficient of Turkey and have the evaluation heading which it is struggled in order to maintain the continuity of process in Arab states.

An important argument of Turkey related to the reform discussions in Arab world is what Turkey represents. The first view is that the evolution of political Islam comprehension in Turkey and coming of AK Party to the power are the evidence of harmony between Islam and democracy. It was thought that Turkish 'experience' showed the possibility of moderation in the political Islam, and the desire of party to act within the democratic rules proved this. As a natural result of this view, it may be summarized that as Turkey tries to come to the agreement with moderate Islamic roots moving away from the strick secular regime, so its potential to become a model of mildness for Islamic world as an example increases. The second view considers the Turkey's democratization and secularism history responsible for the evolution of political Islam in Turkey. According to this assertion, Turkish example proves the importance of institutional structure in the evolution of political Islam with democratic and secular values. It may be discussed what Turkish model means and what the achievements are. Those, who concentrate on emergence of Political Islam and AK Party

government, assert that Turkish example is within the possibility of moderate Islam and proves the harmony of Islam with democracy. This is an important achievement and for example, it was used by US government as antidote against the development of radical Islam worldwide. On the other hand, those, who handled the Turkish experience at a wider framework, captured the democratic, secular, globalization and economic harmonization of Turkey, and emphasized that it represented an important example of Muslim nation as the EU candidate and the member of the important Western organizations such as NATO, OSCE, European Council and OECD for a long time. When one looks at from a wider framework in such way, Turkey's attractiveness should not be limited with AK Party or moderate Islam only; Turkish value is also the product of other factors. Those two different views about Turkey are also shown with the following citations:

Since Turkey is recognized as the reconciler both in Middle East and Western world, it has a unique position. Turkey's Islamic character is important and reassuring for the region. Islam gradually becomes more popular policy in the communities which the distorted democratic applications are executed in Middle East and this explains why Hamas and Hezbollah are so popular together with other reasons. In this context, Turkey is considered that it has the capacity to understand the regional issues and vulnerabilities due to the Islamic government. Furthermore, non-Arabic neighboring countries such as Turkey or Iran tried to fill the gap in the discussion on "leader Arab country". Since the Arab world is mostly Sunni, it feels more intimacy toward Turkey than toward Iran. Beyond this, the military power of Turkey is considered by the countries such as Iraq and Syria.¹⁰⁰ It is a meaningless idea that Turkey's Islamic dimension has Turkey gained the confidence in the Arab world. Turkey is recognized in the region, since it has the legalization and unity that no other country has them regarding both governmental and social characteristics. Turkey has a constitutional system that is resistant against the powerful internal pressures, live economy and legal government. Turkey gives importance to the secularism and at the same time, has also the national proud. Army is under the control of civilians. Except Turkey, all countries in Middle East experience the legalization problems.¹⁰¹

On the other hand, Saudi Arabia which began to lose its confidence toward the Western countries and was the most important country of Middle East, began to see Turkey

¹⁰⁰Körber-Stiftung, Bergdorf Yuvarlak Masa Toplantısı, 20-22 Mart 2009, Beyrut, s. 48.

¹⁰¹<http://www.tesev.org.tr/assets/publications/file/Arap%20Dunyasinda%20Turkiye%20Alg%C4%B1s%C4%B106.2010.pdf>

under the ruling of AK Party as the alternative investment area. A number of economic initiations were started between Saudi Arabia and Turkey. At this framework, the agreement on Establishment of Turkish-Saudi Business Council was signed in Riyadh on 1st October 2003, and the Council started to operate in 2004. Turkey may continue to strengthen the bilateral relations that are formed with the Arab Spring. As the economic breakthroughs strengthen the friendship of two countries, it will have the positive impact on the region. About 500 thousand Turkish citizens visit Saudi Arabia with the occasion of Hajj and Umrah per year, and about 125.000 Turkish citizens work in this country¹⁰². Such positive developments may offer the opportunities to Turkey to increase the Hajj and Umrah figures in 500 thousand in the future periods. Thousands of Hajj candidates in Turkey wait for their turns. The freedom of praying must be provided to the citizens who are late by waiting through the works. Especially, Turkish contractors will carry out the big works regarding the accommodation. At the same time, Saudi Arabia is at the first rank among the Gulf countries and sixth rank worldwide where Turkish contractors are awarded the contracts¹⁰³. Our wish is that the good progression would continue in the bilateral relations. It is our task to build such developments as the culture.

The Process and perceptive parameters after the revolution in Egypt that is another important country are the disappointment for Turkey for a long time. However, some explanations associate the bilateral relations with a problem at the political level only. Egyptian government struggles to pay US\$ 4 billion to the importation monthly under the shadow of estimations that the current account account deficit would reach to US\$ 5 billion after coup this year and spends approximately US\$ 1.5 billion from the reserve available at hand monthly. We may add to this that Egyptian officials, who relied upon the monies from Gulf countries, took more than half of the financial promises (US\$ 7 billion of 12 billion),, but there is not any important impact on the Egyptian economy or Egyptian citizens. Namely, Egypt will need each dollar from foreign investments at the point of directly attracting the foreign investments in contrary to Turkey that is at 13th rank in the world. As seen from this, the conflict of Egyptian officials with Ankara is not economic-oriented, but is experienced at the political plane. Insisting on bilateral relations is not at the rate related to the insisting on continuing of commercial relations and Turkish investments at such time when Egyptian

¹⁰² Bütçe Raporu: www.mfa.gov.tr/site_media/html/butce_2013.pdf.

officials need the foreign investments and economic support much more than ever before. After Egypt announced the interruption of diplomatic relations, the economic relations and continuation of Turkish investments in Egypt were the indicator of this, because Munir Fahri Abdunnur, the Egypt's Minister of Trade and Industry, attracted the attention to the resoluteness of government in separating the economic relations from political attitudes each other, saying "the Ministry sees positive to all Turkish investments for now and in the future and furthermore, will not hesitate to solve all problems which those investments will encounter with". This Minister was followed by Adil Lema who was the President of Turkish-Egyptian Business Council and Chamber of Marine Trade of Port Said during the last crisis. Lema explained that despite of what were experienced between the parties at the political or diplomatic plane, the commercial relations and investments between Egypt and Turkey would be affected by them.¹⁰⁴ In this context, one may evaluate that Turkey didn't collapse at the threshold of big crises where the new perception processes were experienced in Middle East after AK Party ruling.

Globalization process brings the new threats and risk factors together for this century. In this context, Turkey signed the bilateral agreements on today's important issues such as security, drug and terrorism with the states that had the significant impact capacity in the region after AK Party ruling, and made many evaluations and agreements covering many subheadings on PKK terror with the countries in the region. Consequently, AK Party government after 2002 destroyed the negative perception and propaganda processes in Middle East for years and brought Turkey a model country position with the new pragmatic and rational foreign policy perspective as it desired.

¹⁰⁴ Ahmet Uysal, *Devrim Öncesi Mısır'da Türkiye Algısı (2005- 2010)*.

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